

**ABUSE OF POWER IN CHRISTIAN
LEADERSHIP IN IHECHIOWA: A
REFLECTION ON 1 SAMUEL 12:1-5**

BY

**UFERE, GODSWILL OME
(PG/MTH/2021/025)**

**HUGH GOLDIE LAY/THEOLOGICAL
TRAINING INSTITUTION, AROCHUKWU**

**IN AFFILIATION WITH
ABIA STATE UNIVERSITY, UTURU**

MAY, 2024.

REQUIREMENTS

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**REV. DR. THEOPHILUS CHUKWU NGELE
SUPERVISOR**

MAY, 2024.

APPROVAL

This thesis has been read and approved as meeting the requirements for the award of Master in Theology, Hugh Goldie Lay/Theological Training Institution, Arochukwu, in affiliation with Abia State University, Uturu.

Rev. Theophilus Chukwu Ngele, Ph.D
Dip.Theo, BA, BD, MA, Ph.D
Supervisor

Date

Rev. Eme Ndukwe
Dip.Theo, BA, MA (Phil), MTh
Director, SPGS

Date

Rev. Theophilus Chukwu Ngele, Ph.D
Dip.Theo, BA, BD, MA, Ph.D
Rector, HGLTTIA

Date

External Supervisor

Date

DECLARATION

I, Ufere, Godswill Ome, with the registration number PG/MTH/2021/025 hereby sincerely declare that this thesis was originally carried out by me; I acknowledged all the works I made reference to and those interviewed. This work has not been submitted to any other institution for the award of any other diploma or degree except where due acknowledgement has been made in the text.

Ufere, Godswill Ome
Researcher

Date

CERTIFICATION

This is to certify that this thesis titled “Abuse of Power in Christian Leadership in Ihechiowa: A Reflection on 1 Samuel 12:1-5,” was carried out by Ufere, Godswill Ome with the registration number PG/MTH/2021/025 in the School of Post Graduate Studies of Hugh Goldie Lay/Theological Training Institution, Arochukwu, in affiliation with Abia State University, Uturu under my supervision.

Rev. Theophilus Chukwu Ngele, Ph.D
Supervisor

Date

DEDICATION

This research work is dedicated to my father, Eld. Dr. Ome Joseph Ufere—my great example of faith and authenticity and to all students of theology.

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ABSTRACT

This research, “Abuse of Power in Christian Leadership in Ihechiowa: A Reflection on 1 Samuel 12:1-5” addressed the extent to which Christian leaders in the Church have abused power invested into their hands in Ihechiowa. Power which is a vital subject for the church, today has also become the license for promoting abuses in the church. The purpose of this research is to investigate abuse of power in Christian leadership in Ihechiowa, its possible causes, effects and the possible ways of addressing the problem by highlighting Samuel’s example of proper use of power in 1 Samuel 12:1-5. The research is qualitative, thus it adopted descriptive phenomenological and exegetical research methods. It collected data using primary and secondary sources which were presented and analyzed descriptively. The major findings were that, the church that should help man to deal with problems of human life that are significant, persistent, and intolerable has now become the sole problem most people are having in Ihechiowa. Instead of finding fulfillment in the household of the faith, members of the church in Ihechiowa become bound by fear, frustration, indoctrination, and manipulative mind control that have made their pursuit of God an endless drudgery punctuated by a driven and legalistic lifestyle; the contributing factors to this problem are lack of accountability, indiscipline, insecurity, lack of spiritual maturity, poor communication, cultural misunderstandings, and others and such has much effect on the church members, the abusive leader himself and on the power of the gospel. The research recommended that Church leaders in Ihechiowa should embrace humility and rely totally on the Holy Spirit for success in their leadership, church members should speak out when they notice any abuse of power by their church leaders, church leaders should maintain good Christian life worthy of a Christian leader, they need to constantly submit themselves for appraisal for accountability by the church, men and women who aspire to be leaders in the church should be properly scrutinized before they are given such responsibilities by the church. With these and others being applied, churches in Ihechiowa will be sanctuaries not prisons, where faith would be the ultimate freedom not the ultimate trap caused by abuse of power by their leaders.

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CHAPTER ONE

INTRODUCTION

1.1 Background of the Study

Power is a significant factor in all types of leadership. However, the manner in which leaders wield power determines their moral standing in the realm of leadership. Christian leaders are no exception to this rule. Since power plays a pivotal role in leadership, particularly for Christian leaders, it is imperative that they exercise power judiciously in harmony with Christian principles. Catherine Keller eloquently explained that, “Any reflection about power is at the same time an act of power—an exercise of influence within the matrix of relations, itself demanding accountability” (58). Christian leaders in Ihechiowa impact the actions and perceptions of their members through the power they wield. They must embody Christian ethics and guide a congregation in their Christian practices with unwavering dedication. Unfortunately, some of the Christian leaders abuse the power invested in their hands.

The manner in which the Christian leaders in Ihechiowa exert power and the manner in which the church members respond to the leaders result in conscious and subconscious preconceptions and perceptions that induce actions and reactions from both sides. The way Christian leaders relate with the members portrays whether the lifestyle of the leaders are in order or not. Christian leadership referring to leaders who have leadership responsibilities within a Christian organization are rooted in the Christian faith and have a specifically Christian purpose. Also, it is the process of helping a congregation embody in its corporate life the practices that shape vital Christian life, community, and witness in ways that are faithful to Jesus Christ and the gospel and appropriate to the particular congregation’s setting, resources, and purpose. Thus, in this case, Christian leadership in Ihechiowa means leadership by Christians within the Church.

In Ihechiowa, abuse of power in Christian leadership set in when those in spiritual positions of authority can violate our trust. It is possible to become so determined to defend a spiritual place of authority, a doctrine, or a way of doing things, that one would and abuse anyone who questions, disagrees, or does not “behave” spiritually the way one wants them to. When one’s words and actions tear down another, or attack or weaken a person’s standing as a Christian – to gratify oneself, one’s position, or beliefs, while, at the same time, weakening or harming another – that is an abuse. This means that abuse of power occurs in the church context when church leaders resort to unjust means, such as, misrepresenting scripture, manipulation, fear tactics, or even outright use of physical force, to

coerce their followers into doing their bidding, so that their self-interests are appeased or complied with. Many Church leaders in Ihechiowa thrive on corruption, some take advantage of the psychology of an average Christians who is always in search of miracles and wonders, and they exploit their followers financially and materially. These are proofs of abuse of power in Christian leadership in Ihechiowa.

Illustratively, in the Presbyterian Church of Nigeria, one of the ministers that have pastored the parish there was always fond of verbally abusing his members from the pulpit; he called them poor people without future. He also threatened slapping some of the older women who always tried to sleep during preaching. He also initiated a “Good morning” offering every Sunday morning which was done immediately after procession into the church. He used the money and even gave his personal freewill and plate offerings from that money. Such case is also reported of in Christ Ascension Church, where the new prophet sent to the church teamed up with the evangelist there and compelled their members to buy particular herbs they made for any healing prayed for in the church to be effective. This led to conflict between the three church leaders there (the pastor with the evangelist and prophet).

In another occasion, a pastor was found guilty of impregnating two of his church members and attempted aborting the pregnancy by himself in his room. Luck ran out of him when one of the girls had severe bleeding and there was need to carry her to the hospital to save her life at least. In the Apostolic Church, the pastor always had issues with the members and whenever any of them wanted to make peace with him, he will tell the person to bring three-leaf yam to appease him else he will not forgive the person, this landed him to be dubbed “*Ori ona*” (eater of three-leaf yam) by the youths of the community. That was very shameful of his position as a Christian leader.

Christian leaders are seen not only as the representatives of God among men, but also as priests who represent the people before God. Consequently, there are high spiritual and moral expectations from them since they are supposed to be persons of good standing in the society. The reverse is the case in some churches in Ihechiowa; the abuse of power among Christian leaders in Ihechiowa has reached an alarming rate as within short interval stories of the misdeeds of some supposed leaders in the Church are heard.

The situation above indeed is worrisome and calls for immediate action to save the church and the entire society from further deterioration. This research, as it exposes the unwholesome use of power

among some Church leaders in Ihechiowa shall be a response to this clarion call for the Christian leaders in Ihechiowa to conduct their ministries with proper use of ministerial power.

1.2 Statement of Problem

The problem leading to this research is the abuse of power by some church leaders in Ihechiowa and the problems arising from the abuse. Power is highly abused among some church leaders, which is not supposed to be so. Proper use or exercise of power by Church leaders has been bastardized which consequently has led to poor administration or leadership in the Church. In some of the churches in Ihechiowa, there is improper administrative power use. Some church leaders take advantage of their members. Serious complaints are made by members of the Churches and the society at large over the attitude of pastors, evangelists and deacons who used their power to perpetrate ills in the church and the community where their church is situated in Ihechiowa.

The abuse of power in Ihechiowa has resulted to poor church growth or membership and at worst poor Christian living. Most individuals and families in Ihechiowa and the entire society are inflicted with pain and sorrow through the conducts and practices of Christian leaders who abuse their power. As a result of this abuse, the gospel of Christ has begun to lose relevance in Ihechiowa. As a result of this, the gospel of Jesus Christ and his kingdom has inherent transforming power, it is expected that Christian leaders in Ihechiowa will lead their congregations to transform society by their speech and lifestyle. The church leaders' failure in this regard by abusing their power greatly hampers the effective spread of the gospel in the community. Some non-converts in Ihechiowa will vow never to be converted because of how a particular pastor of a church behaves. The abuse has also muddied the face of Christianity and detracted from the expected positive effects of Christian testimony and the gospel in the eyes of the bewildered watching public in Ihechiowa. The gospel has become anthropocentric rather than theocentric and Christocentric and as a result, society sinks deeper into corruption and decay and, even worse, many souls are being lost in Ihechiowa community.

1.3 Research Questions

Based on the premise that abuse of power occurs in Church leadership, the research attempts to answer the following main research question with the help of the four sub-questions: What institutes the abuse of power of Christian leaders in Ihechiowa and how can it be addressed?

1. How is power abused among Christian leaders in Ihechiowa?

2. What are the causes of abuse of power of Christian leaders in Ihechiowa?
3. What are the effects of the abuse of power in Christian leadership on the church, most especially on the church leaders themselves and the society?
4. What lessons can Christian leaders in Ihechiowa learn from Samuel's use of power as testified to in 1 Samuel 12:1-5?
5. What other strategies can be used to prevent the abuse of power in Christian leadership in Ihechiowa?

1.4 Purpose of the Study

The researcher considering the level of abuse of power in Christian leadership in Ihechiowa, delved into this research with the following purposes or aims:

1. The primary aim or purpose of this research work is to investigate abuse of power in Christian leadership in Ihechiowa.
2. The examine possible causes of abuse of power among Christian leaders in Ihechiowa.
3. The investigate the effects of abuse of power in Christian leadership on the church, the perpetrators and the society.
4. It also highlights the acceptable behaviour expected of Christian leaders in Ihechiowa, using Samuel's example of proper use of power in 1 Samuel 12:1-5 as exemplar.
5. The research also looks into possible ways of addressing the problem of abuse of power in Christian leadership in Ihechiowa.

1.5 Significance of the Study

The significance of this research are as mentioned below:

1. This research will help the church authority to know the reality of the problem in Ihechiowa.
2. It will create awareness on the part of Christian leaders on the importance of proper exercise of power and how the neglects of such can lead to abuses.
3. This study will be of immense importance to church leaders as it will first of all open their eyes to the issues of the church as it concerns the abuse of power in Christian leadership today.
4. It will help Christian leaders to know the strategies that can be used to effectively prevent and deal with the abuse of power in Christian leadership in Ihechiowa.

5. The research has academic value as it will contribute to the disciplines of Christian leadership and ethics by being helpful in developing further studies on the subject matter and being a relevant source of literature.

1.6 Scope of Study

The scope of the research is Ihechiowa in Arochukwu Local Government Area of Abia State. The study used 1 Samuel 12:1-5 as a pointer to the churches in Ihechiowa. Ihechiowa as a clan has eighteen (17) villages. It is divided into two parts: Eleoha and Ikwun. Eleoha consists of seven (7) villages (Amamiri, Achara, Okpo, Nkporo, Amafia, Amaetiti, and Umuchiakuma) while Ikwun has ten (10) villages (Obinto, Atan, Umuzomgbo, Umuye, Agbo, Uburu, Ndiokpo, Ebuoru, Ebemofia, Obichie).

The research work will only concentrate on churches in Amammiri in Eleoha of Ihechiowa because of the large number of churches in Ihechiowa. The six churches covered in Amammiri are Presbyterian Church of Nigeria, Assemblies of God Church, The Apostolic Church, Evangel Church, Divine Foundation Church and Christ Ascension Church. Issues discussed in the work include: concept of power, power in leadership, ethics and power, abuse of power, nature of power abusive leaders, nature of the victims of abuse of power, effects of abuse of power, concept of leadership, concept of ethical leadership, exegetical study of 1 Samuel 12:1-5, theological conclusions and abuse of power in Christian leadership in Ihechiowa.

The research was limited to Christian leadership in the Church; it never included Christian leadership in Christian religious organizations or businesses. Christian leadership in this research refers to church leaders (such as pastors, elders, deacons and administrators).

1.7 Methodology

The research is qualitative and adopted descriptive phenomenological and exegetical research methods. The descriptive phenomenological method sought to describe accurately the eventual manifestations or of abuse of power in Ihechiowa. It collected data using primary sources such as oral interviews, testimonies, unpublished materials. The researcher interviewed members and church leaders from the churches; and secondary sources, which include published textbooks, newspapers, seminar papers, dissertations, Bible commentaries, journals, magazines and internet materials. All data were

descriptively analyzed and presented. The researcher also adopted a survey research method as a result of the number of churches covered.

1.8 Limitation of the Study

The researcher had some limitations at the time in carried out this research.

1. **Financial Constraint:** Insufficient fund impeded the efficiency of the research in sourcing for the relevant materials, literature or information and in the process of data collection (internet and interviews).
2. **Attitude of Respondents:** The attitude of respondents was another problem. Some respondents were not so open to narrate totally the nature of abuse of power by their church leaders as experienced in their church.
3. **Scarcity of Materials:** The researcher did not have access to enough materials on the concept of abuse of power in the church written by Africa authors.

However in all, the researcher by the grace of God overcame all these limitations and the research was carried out.

1.9 Definition of Terms

In a research of this nature, it is pertinent to give the working definitions of some major words used in the research.

Power

This is possession of controlling influence. It is also the possession of the qualities (especially mental) required to do something or get something done (*WordWeb*, n.pg). In this research, power shall be seen as the possession of controlling influence.

Abuse

This is defined as improper treatment; application to a wrong or bad purpose and unjust, corrupt or wrongful practice or custom (*Online English Dictionary*, n.pg). According to *WordWeb*, abuse is use to one's advantage in a way that that was not intended (n.pg). The latter definition will be preferred for the purpose of this research.

Leadership

According to Chand, "Leadership is an art whereby an individual influences a group of individuals for achieving a common set of goals: whose end must be reached when sets of rules are followed" (quoted by Janvier and Thaba 19). Leadership, according to Zeitchik is about inspiring others to pursue your vision within the parameters you set, to the extent that it becomes a shared effort, a shared vision, and a shared success (13). Kruse as well sees leadership as a process of social influence, which maximizes the efforts of others, towards the achievement of a goal (23). For the purpose of this research, Zeitchik's definition fits more in defining leadership in the context of power.

Christian Leadership

Kessler and Kretzschmar present two ways of using the term "Christian leadership": first, Christians who lead within a Church or Christian organization that has its base in the Christian faith (e.g. a church, mission agency, non-profit organization); and secondly, Christians who lead in secular organizations (e.g. businesses, companies, government, secular non-profit organizations) and desire to reflect a "Christian worldview, anthropology and set of values" (2). For this research, the first definition is used, that is, one who leads within a Church or a Christian organization.

Church

It is a building set aside for public worship, especially that of a parish, and especially that of an established or once established form of the Christian religion (Allen 295). An Online Theological Dictionary defines church as the collective body of Christians, or all those over the face of the earth who profess to believe in Christ, and acknowledge him to be the Saviour of mankind: this is called the visible church; it is also understood to be an assembly of Christians meeting in one place for the solemn worship of God (n.pg). The latter definition of Church by the theological dictionary is preferable for the sake of this research.

1.10 Organization of the Study

This research work has been systematically organized in chapters. Its preliminary pages comprise of the title page, the approval page, the declaration page, the certification page, the dedication page, acknowledgement page, the abstract and table of contents.

Chapter one, which has to do with the introduction, was structured as follows: background of the study, statement of the problem, research questions, purpose of the study, significance of the study, scope of the study, research methodology, limitation of the study, definition of terms and organization of the study. Chapter two has to do with the literature review which has to do with the views of scholars as it relates to the topic, and it comprises of power in leadership, concept of abuse of power, nature of power abusive leaders, nature of the victims of abuse of power, the effects of abuse of power, differentiating power and authority, concept of leadership, ethical theories of leadership, concept of Christian leadership and summary of literature review.

Chapter three handles the exegetical study of 1 Samuel 12:1-5. In this chapter, the researcher focused on the following: background of 1 Samuel 12:1-5, contexts of I Samuel 12:1-5, text of I Samuel 12:1-5, delineation of I Samuel 12:1-5, exegesis of 1 Samuel 12:1-5 and theological conclusions. Chapter four looked into the abuse of power in Christian leadership in Ihechiowa. The following sub-headings were handled in this chapter: brief history of Ihechiowa, abuse of power in Christian leadership in Ihechiowa, causes of abuse of power among Christian leaders in Ihechiowa, effects of abuse of power among Christian leaders in Ihechiowa, lessons for Christian leaders in Ihechiowa from Samuel's use of power as testified to in 1 Samuel 12:1-5 and other strategies for preventing abuse of power among Christian leaders in Ihechiowa.

Chapter five covers summary of findings, recommendation and conclusion. Here, the summary of findings, recommendations, contributions to knowledge, suggestions for further studies and conclusion were done.

CHAPTER TWO

LITERATURE REVIEW

The literature review of this research is for the examination of scholarly works related to the research. Mouton describes the importance of the literature review, as he said that, it is important to discover how others have investigated the problem that is being researched, and to establish what their research has produced (86-87). Ituma adds that “It is the review of related topics that help a researcher to determine the research gap which in turn will help the researcher to create the research problem” (46). It is possible to learn about the available research focuses that has been used in the past. This results in ensuring that the research is not simply duplicating what others have already written on. Additionally, it is necessary to discover the most current concepts about the issues under discussion and the most widely accepted findings on these topics. The literature review also offers the most generally accepted definitions on the major topics and exposes the areas that call for further research.

2.1 Power in Leadership

In the opinion of Whitehead and Whitehead, "power is not much as something in itself, but a process that turns into a person and between a group of individuals. For them, “To mature is to grow in power” (83). “Power is more a process than a thing. Power points to something that happens between people, something going on, an interaction. Power is not so much a possession as a way of relating” (Whitehead and Whitehead 150). Whitehead and Whitehead differentiate between personal power and social power. Whereas personal power “points to my awareness of myself as strong, the ways I find myself capable or coercive in interaction with others” (150), social power refers to the strength in the group and the authority of the organization or group. It is “an awareness of the differences in strength among us – what these differences are and how we will deal with them” (Whitehead and Whitehead 150). Social power and personal power are related to each other in that an individual becomes aware of his/her personal power through group interaction. In the following points, dimensions of personal power, as well as the development of power in an individual are discussed.

2.1.1 Dimensions of Personal Power

Whitehead and Whitehead identify five dimensions of personal power. Thus,

- i. Power On (initiative and influence adult competence)

- ii. Power Over (coordination and control organizational leadership)
- iii. Power Against (competition and conflict assertion and negotiation)
- iv. Power For (service and nurturance parenthood and ministry)
- v. Power With (mutuality and collaboration interdependence and dependability) (151).

i. Power On: Realizing one's influence on the environment leads to independence and adult competence. Lack of confidence results in over-dependency and inadequacy, leading to abusive behavior towards subordinates (Whitehead and Whitehead 152).

ii. Power Over: An individual learns to influence, and to take charge of a situation, managing the power of others. This power over or control is not negative (and is actually necessary to an extent for organizational leadership) if it is exercised to reach a common goal with accountability, resisting the temptation to manipulate others. It is realized through the coordination. When this power fails, teams become ineffective because decisions are not made, resources are not utilized, and energy is lost. However, there is uneasiness about this face of power because of the fear of control and manipulation, which could result in the abuse of power (Whitehead and Whitehead 153).

iii. Power Against: An individual learns to deal maturely with competition and conflict, even to stand against the power of others and survive. This strength is necessary to work out differences with colleagues and family members and to maintain integrity, standing up against the wrong. On the other hand, there is a fear of using this power and entering conflicts that become destructive and abusive. It is important to be able to mediate and work out conflicts to avoid the destructive end that confrontations can have and to use the power one has to become abusive in order to win each conflict (Whitehead and Whitehead 155).

iv. Power For: An individual must be aware of their power to be strong for others, understanding strengths and weaknesses. This awareness involves caring for others, crucial for family and ministry. Without a nurturing and servant attitude, empowerment is hindered. Dominance over others rather than for them can lead to tension and potential abuse of power (Whitehead and Whitehead 157).

v. Power With: This dimension of power recognizes individual strength, but realizes the importance of coming together to be strong together – “the ability to enjoy mutual influence and mutual empowerment” (158). It means interdependence and mutual dependability: I depend on others and they,

in turn, can depend on me. The dimensions of power are relevant for leadership and maturity in exercising power in leadership. While the dimensions of power can be used to have a positive influence on others, they can result in the abuse of power if not developed in the individual or kept in check through organizational accountability. The development of this power in the following section is closely linked to the five dimensions of power.

2.1.2 Levels of Development of Individual power

McClelland in his book, *Power: The Inner Experience*, present important insights into power and how it develops in individuals through their lifetime. This process is significant for leadership and how the leader exerts his/her power, as well as how the person perceives the exertion of power from others (116). McClelland's book, "Power: The Inner Experience," explores power development in individuals over a lifetime. It is crucial for leadership and how power is perceived. There are four levels of power development, influenced by life experiences and cultural pressures. These levels differ from Jim Collins' classification of leadership effectiveness. Level 5 leaders exhibit personal humility and professional will, setting them apart from levels 1 to 4.

McClelland's four levels of development of power in an individual are based on a lifelong process that begins in childhood and carries on to adulthood. These four levels are used differently from the level 5 classification by Jim Collins, where the focus is on capability, competence and effectiveness of leaders and executives in adulthood. Collins claims that a level 5 leader exhibits the qualities of personal humility and professional will, distinguishing him/herself by greatness, in comparison to the level 1 to 4 leaders: level 1 – highly capable, level 2 – contributing team member, level 3 – competent manager, level 4 – effective leader (119-123).

The first level of experiencing power is receptivity, where individuals open up to the strength of others. This power is developed through love and support received during childhood and adulthood. Healing from hurts and feeling empowered are key aspects of this level. Autonomy is the second level, focusing on independence and managing life as an adult. Failure to move beyond autonomy can result in feeling inadequate or powerless. The third level involves using developed power to influence the social environment positively, but it can also lead to an abuse of power if not managed properly. The final level, "We," emphasizes cooperation and the value of others' contributions, marking a mature leader who welcomes input from others.

Receptivity allows individuals to feel empowered by the strength of others, leading to a sense of safety and support. Autonomy is about achieving independence and managing life as an adult, but it is crucial to move beyond this level to avoid feeling inadequate. The third level involves using power to influence the social environment positively, but it can also lead to an abuse of power if not managed correctly. The final level, "We," emphasizes cooperation and the value of others' contributions, marking a mature leader who welcomes input from others.

2.1.3 Forms of Power

French and Raven's model of power and leadership focuses on the different forms of power that leaders can use to influence group members. They identified five primary forms of power: coercive, reward, legitimate, referent, and expert, with an additional form added later by Raven: informational power. Kessler further divides referent power into power by relations and power by charisma. The model by French and Raven explores how power impacts leadership and the success of a leader in influencing others within a group or organization. They studied the behavior of those exerting power and the reactions of those subjected to that power. The dimensions of power and its development in individuals are crucial aspects to consider when examining leadership and social influence.

John R.P. French and Bertram Raven's research delves into the relationship between power and influence, emphasizing the significance of understanding how leaders exert power and how it affects their ability to lead effectively. The six identified power bases play a vital role in shaping leadership dynamics and outcomes within social contexts (540), but this research concentrates only on the following six power bases.

i. Coercive Power

This power is leading through force, threat or punishment; can be personal or impersonal. A coercive power base involves leading through force, threat or punishment, which can be effective if the threat is believable and feasible. However, this power base is often used when no other methods are available and the leader has a personal need for attention, requiring the submission of his/her followers. The application of coercive power can be personal (termination of position, transfer to a worse position, or invoking physical pain) and impersonal (devaluation, rejection or ignoring others). Thus, it becomes clear that coercive power could be effective if an organization is experiencing a crisis, and the leader needs to make clear decisions and give clear instructions to all without discussion. On the other hand,

coercive power can destroy an organization if the leader becomes a dictator and will not acknowledge the strengths and valuable contributions of the colleagues (Kessler 540).

ii. Reward Power

This form of power offers rewards for obedience, performance or compliance; can be personal or impersonal. A reward power base refers to the right to offer rewards to someone for obedience, performance or compliance. It also includes the power of a leader to deny others something for failing to meet the expectations of the leader. The reward power base can be further divided into two categories: impersonal rewards (promise of rewards in the form of material resources) and personal rewards (receiving approval from key people, compliments, attention and acceptance). Reward power can be used by a leader to motivate the followers and increase their production levels. At the same time, this power can be abused in that rewards are granted as a form of bribery to gain the support of some of the subordinates. Using reward power to withhold rewards can result in a form of punishment or showing favouritism, leading to unfair treatment (Kessler 42).

iii. Legitimate Power

This power is given to a person when placed in a position by election, selection or appointment. A legitimate power base is the power given to a person when placed in a position by election, selection or appointment. A structural hierarchy is important in order for this power base to function, and is based on cultural values (acceptance of these structures and the designation of the leader). This power base can be used to serve those who have placed trust in the leader by electing, selecting or appointing that person. The power base can be misused by taking on the position and considering oneself to have been given the authority without feeling a sense of accountability (Kessler 42-43).

iv. Referent Power

Referent power is based on the group and the organizational affiliations that a leader has. A referent power base is based on the group and the organizational affiliations that a leader has. This has positive and negative references, depending on how the affiliation is viewed. It also involves charm and admiration, and can be useful in combination with other forms of power. This power base is used by the charismatic leader who draws followers through personality and the ability to motivate people. Its negative side is the danger of the formation of in- and out-groups, which could lead to organizational divisions (Kessler 43).

v. Expert Power

This is power based on the information the leader has, experience and credentials of the leader. An expert power base is present if a member of the organization has access to information, and can decide as to whether or not s/he shares the information. It is based on what one knows as well as the experience and credentials that one possesses. It is important that others perceive that the person has expertise in order to grant the leader power. Positive expert power results in positive influence, whereas negative expert power results in opposition to the expert's instructions. This could be the result if a leader flaunts his/her credentials and does not accept inputs from others because s/he claims to know all there is to know in a given situation (Kessler 44).

vi. Informational Power

This power is based on the influence that a leader has in possessing knowledge and information that is important for others to have. The informational power base is the influence that a person has in possessing knowledge that is important for others to have (for example national security data, personnel information etc.). Direct informational power results in being able to have a direct influence on others, and indirect informational power has an indirect influence on others. In examining these power bases closely, it becomes evident that, depending on how a leader applies the power base in a leadership position, as well as in a specific situation, the results can be positive or negative, as was also evident with the faces of personal power. A leader's ability and willingness for honest self-reflection is a valuable asset and is beneficial in preventing abusive behaviour (Kessler 44-45).

The power forms from French and Raven are helpful for leaders to reflect on the personal power base that they apply in the various types of leadership positions in which the leaders find themselves. Self-reflection should result in an awareness of the bases that could incite the abuse of power in certain situations. Leaders should ask themselves which power bases they possess, and which power bases they should apply in various settings in a leadership position in an organization. Plueddemann refers to this as situational leadership, and views the ability of a leader to adapt the appropriate leadership style to the situation as essential for managing multicultural teams (153).

2.2 Concept of Abuse of Power

According to Nunez and Gonzalez, the abuse of power in Christian organizations is referred to as "mobbing", and can be defined as continual, repeated aggression that is expressed in non-verbal cues,

words and behaviour that has a negative impact on the victim's dignity and the organizational climate (36). It is important to note that the abuse of power does not refer to a single incident, but rather a behavioural pattern that develops over a period of time and repeatedly takes place. Furthermore, it is often assumed that a leader intentionally abuses his/her power. However, the abuse can also be unintentional and the leader may be unaware of the way in which the colleagues perceive his/her behavior.

2.2.1 Types of Abuse of Power

In general, when abuse is mentioned, it is being associated with sexual, physical or psychological abuse. Unfortunately, these more apparent forms of abuse are more prevalent than anyone cared to admit in the past. Physical or sexual abuse takes place when persons are treated in a way that damages them physically or sexually. Psychological abuse is associated with brainwashing, and attacking others on an emotional level (Winter 25). Oakley states that spiritual abuse cannot be incorporated into models of other types of abuse. However, it is necessary that this form of abuse be clearly recognized as a specific form of abuse (56).

However, the abuse discussed in this dissertation is a spiritual and emotional form of abuse that can leave deep wounds and results in people experiencing emotional damage and having a "hard time trusting a spiritual system again" (Johnson and van Vonderen 50). According to Winter, "If mobbing occurs on a spiritual level it is referred to as spiritual abuse. Spirituality can be misused as a tool to abuse employees, making them feel that they must endure the mistreatment in order to be a good Christian and to fulfil the mission of the organization" (25). This abuse can take place in various ways: Leaders quote Scripture to measure their followers' commitment or calling, communicating an individual's unsuitability for a task, pressuring people to resign by degrading them in front of others, demoting people or reducing their salary (without informing them), providing limited or biased information about an employee in a meeting, leaving a negative impression of that employee, falsely accusing subordinates in front of others, withholding recognition (allegedly so that the employee will not become proud), and employees not being given the opportunity to defend themselves. Spiritual abuse can be the result of "uncertain, tentative and ineffective" (Kretzschmar 47) leaders who compensate for their insecurity by becoming domineering and coercive, leading to conflicts and mismanagement of resources. Individuals and organizations suffer long term effects from this type of immoral or immature character.

2.2.2 The Hierarchical Abuse of Power

Vredenburg and Brender have extensively researched the hierarchical abuse of power in work organizations. Their research led to the formation of the process model that conceptualizes the abusive exercise of power. It is a “linear representation of a set of variables that define a theoretically meaningful sequence of related conditions and actions” (Vredenburg and Brender 1341). This model portrays how “individual attributes and organizational conditions interact as individuals make decisions and undertake actions that have outcomes” (1341). It is beneficial for this dissertation as it summarizes the motives, attributes, conditions and sources, decisions, strategies and outcomes of the abusive exercise of power in organizations.

The hierarchical abuse of power is defined as “acts which manifest disrespect for a subordinate’s dignity or provide obstacles to a subordinate’s performance or deserved rewards” (Vredenburg and Brender 1339). According to them, the abusive exercise of power violates ethical standards in four main categories: 1) “If individuals deserve dignity in and of themselves, workplaces should not allow the managerial exercise of power to devalue the human worthiness of a subordinate” 2) Subordinates have a right to “privacy, truthfulness and safety, which acts of power abuse often violate” 3) The abuse of power is unethical when it violates the norms and laws of the community (e.g. if a manager interferes with the performance of a subordinate, or denies rewards). 4) Fairness and justice cannot be practiced selectively by a leader (e.g. being friendly or overly supportive to some and unfair to others) (1344). They go on to say that organizational hierarchies carry the potential for abuse because they can be conducive to determining the actions of subordinates by determining the acquisition or the withholding of rewards, being allowed to reach personal goals, combined with privilege and prestige for some, and manipulating those with less power.

Vredenburg and Brender define two aspects of power that cause managers to be prone to abusing their power:

1. Relational nature: Subordinates are dependent on their authority for rewards.
2. Non-rational use: Organizations are contexts of manifest and latent conflicts (1338).

These conflicts can develop into a political or emotional issue, resulting in power being used for non-rational conflict behaviour in an organization. Two premises for the exercise of power underlie the concept of hierarchical abuse:

1. The power-holder can exercise power to increase or decrease the subordinate's feelings of dignity and self-respect. Some examples of this type of abusive exercise of power are demanding cooperation in illegal proceedings, physical harassment, verbal harassment or public embarrassment, insisting on conformity, harmful gossip, lying, exaggerating or making promises that one cannot keep.

2. He/She can exercise power to diminish the subordinate's work performance and acquisition of deserved rewards. This may occur when the manager accepts credit for the work that his/her subordinate has done, depriving subordinates of the resources that are necessary for the task at hand, attributing one's own poor performance to other's performance, and discriminating against subordinates in performance appraisals. Frequent abuse of power results in the acceptability of the abusive behaviour, and can result in the formation of new norms within an organization.

2.2.3 Powerholders' Motives and Attributes

According to Vredenburg and Brender's findings, the primary causes of abuse of power come from the leader's lack of moral motives and attributes. This includes the need for control, the desire for personal service, achieving personal and/or organizational goals, the need for expressions of loyalty and obedience, as well as punishing or favouring individuals. The attributes that were identified in pursuing the motives are a high need for power with "little self-control, impulsiveness, emotional immaturity, dominance, and manipulateness" (1342). The research determined that defensive, insecure behaviour is more likely when self-esteem is low. Further attributes found to be associated with the abuse of power are egocentrism, caring little for others, ethical insensitivity, a tendency to take risks as well as emotionalism. These motives and attributes are situated at the onset of the model, indicating that they are present at the onset of the process and initiate it (Vredenburg and Brender 1342).

2.2.4 Organizational Conditions and Power Sources

Vredenburg and Brender identified organizational conditions that contribute to power abuse:

- Lack of clear decision-making structure leads to individual decisions
 - Uncertainty in work processes and goals affects abuse
 - Culture of secrecy instead of transparency
 - Performance pressure from management
- Four main sources of power that lead to abuse:
- Structural position and hierarchical authority
 - Control over resources

- Personal appeal of individuals
- Past events not addressed (1343).

It is interesting to note that these sources of power are related to some of French and Raven's power bases/forms: structural position is related to the coercive and legitimate power forms. The control of resources is related to the expert and informational power forms. The personal appeal is related to the referent power form, and the events from the past can be related to the reward power form in that the past can be used in order to reward or punish people according to what they may or may not have done.

2.2.5 Decisions, Strategies and Outcomes

Powerholders' motives and attributes initiate abuse, while organizational conditions and sources of power contribute to it. Leaders calculate the risk of abusing power, with submissive followers reducing the risk. Organizational norms can limit abuse. Strategies for abuse depend on various factors. Outcomes can be unintended or intended. Vredenburg and Brender provide an analysis of abusive power dynamics. Structures are crucial for preventing abuse. Poor structures lead to corruption, injustice, and abuse.

2.3 Nature of Power Abusive Leaders

Winter says, "Evidently others who had been promoted in the company changed and succumbed to the temptation of the new sense of empowerment they felt in their leadership position as captain" (29). Coleman sums it up in this way: Every legitimate power succumbs to the temptation to expand power beyond its legitimate spheres ... every form of empirical legitimate power is inherently instable since insecurity, interest, and special perspective will tempt the holders of it to move beyond legitimate power to an exercise of more power not within their domain and right (Coleman 39). This quote from Coleman suggests that an insecure leader who has his/her personal interests and perspectives in mind will be tempted to become abusive. What are the possible temptations that a leader struggles with? Which aspects of leadership are conducive to abuse of power? As Osmer would ask: Why is this (abuse of power) happening? The following sub-section will address aspects that define abusive leaders in an attempt to find answers to these questions: the temptations that leaders encounter, moral character, personality disorders, power seekers, lack of clarity and insecurity.

2.3.1 Possible Temptations

Whereas Coleman says that leaders will be tempted by insecurity, interest, and special perspective (42), Henri Nouwen states that leaders face the temptation to be relevant, spectacular and powerful, using the temptations of Jesus as presented in Matthew 4:1-11 as an example (23). These are significant not only for the topic of ethical leadership, but also for the issue of abuse. Depending on whether or not a leader falls into the temptation to be relevant, spectacular or powerful will have an effect on whether the leadership will be perceived as ethical or abusive.

i. The Temptation to be Relevant

Nouwen discusses Jesus' first temptation in Matthew 4, where Satan tempts him to turn stones into bread. This temptation is seen as a desire for relevance over doing what is right. Christian leaders may feel irrelevant in a secular society, but they must resist the temptation to prioritize popularity over righteousness. Leaders should be rooted in a deep relationship with Jesus and have informed opinions on current issues to avoid falling into the trap of seeking relevance.

Nouwen emphasizes the importance of prayer in maintaining flexibility, conviction, and gentleness in leadership. Leaders who prioritize popularity over righteousness risk causing disunity and instability within the Church. It is crucial for leaders to make decisions based on what is right and beneficial for the people and the organization, rather than seeking popularity. Being rooted in prayer allows leaders to remain true witnesses without being manipulative or offensive.

ii. The Temptation to be Spectacular

The second temptation that Nouwen refers to in Matthew 4 is Satan challenging Jesus to throw himself down from the parapet and letting the angels catch him – the temptation to be spectacular. Nouwen observes that: “Stardom and individual heroism, which are such obvious aspects of our competitive society, are not at all alien to the church. There too the dominant image is that of the self-made man or woman who can do it alone” (56). He warns against individualism in leadership, doing everything yourself and not being accountable to others, in other words, ministry is communal. The problem of celebrity, which occurs when a leader receives compliments to the point of gaining a false sense of importance and accomplishment: leadership is exercised “through an increasingly assumed (and artificial) credibility” (Balda and Balda 38). Accountability keeps this tendency in check. “Celebrity without community is toxic” (39) and community provides the necessary accountability to prevent

toxicity. This temptation is associated with the third level of power development that Whitehead and Whitehead defined as discussed in subsection 2.1.2. For Winter, The experience of success and confirmation can result in leaders claiming that success for their own, ignoring the contribution of the entire team: replacing the “we” with “I”. It can lead to an intolerance of the ideas of others and desiring to stand in the limelight as a leader and receiving the credit for all successes (31).

iii. The Temptation to be Powerful

Nouwen discusses the temptation of power in Matthew 4, where Satan tries to make Jesus bow down for all kingdoms. Power can be tempting as it seems easier than love. Many Christian leaders choose power over healthy relationships. Reflecting on leadership requires spiritual growth in body, mind, and heart (77). Kessler's ethical guidelines support avoiding the temptation of power. Power is a gift from God and should be used to glorify Him. Jesus emphasized worshiping and serving God, not seeking personal gain through power.

2.3.2 Moral Character

A further essential characteristic that defines Christian leaders is moral character. There may be a tendency to assume that certain personality types tend to be more abusive than others, especially if a leader has a dominant personality. However, Kessler and Kessler claim that the abuse of power and authority cannot be assigned only to the dominant personality. A conscientious person can become abusive and controlling (often indirectly), acting on the need to ensure the welfare of the organization, just as the influential leader can control others through persuasive strengths, demanding their attention. The steady leader can control others through resisting change due to the need for a high level of security. The decisive factor is the issue of motive that determines whether the leader allows his/her personality and character to be transformed, and whether the result is to do what is good and right, or to harm others (58-59). Using Diotrophes in 3 John as an example, Kessler and Kessler point out some of the characteristics of a person who is abusive. Diotrophes was an influential person in the church who misused his position to boost his person and implement his will: He “wants to be first”. This resulted in people being denied access to the church, being expelled from the church, as well as gossiping maliciously about the author of the letter (who introduces himself as the “elder”), resulting in a lack of trust (24). From this case study it becomes evident that an abusive leader creates restlessness in the organization, is looking for attention, and is often a determinative loner. Lovas refers to this as boredom. This person is bored in a peaceful, harmonious environment where the fruit of the Spirit is

evident in the group. The goal is to stir up the group and stand in the limelight and gain attention (39). Thus, the boredom is exchanged for power.

Such a person does not accept criticism or correction, gossips about others who question him/her, undermining trust amongst the people, prepared to create divisions by finding support within the group. The abusive leader attempts to make the “support team” dependent, often making others feel guilty if they do not perform as desired. This person is known to change decisions made in the past without consulting others. He/she is not prepared to listen to reminders from critics. Anyone who may seem dangerous to the power-player is removed. S/he lies or twists the truth, down-plays issues, puts others down, tries to force others to trust him/her, claiming to be in a position of authority by God, and accusing others of being abusive. Moral character is more significant than personality, and it became clear that any personality found in a leader can be used to do good or to bring harm. However, personality disorders in leaders can result in abusive behaviour (Lovas 41).

2.3.3 Personality Disorders

According to de Vries, a surprising percentage of leaders have some sort of personality disorder and that a leader’s mental health has a direct and major impact on the morale and structure of the working environment. “Toxic leaders create unhappy workplaces” (de Vries2). In extreme situations, the leaders may exhibit common personality disorders, and it is important to be able to identify the symptoms of the four most frequently identifiable disorders in leaders. The symptoms of the disorders are:

1. If the leader has a passive-aggressive disorder s/he is afraid to assert him/herself, avoids confrontation and is covertly aggressive. The person tends “to use procrastination, inefficiency and forgetfulness to avoid fulfilling obligations” (de Vries 4).
2. The emotionally disconnected or alexithymic leader “finds it difficult to understand the emotions of others and can fear these emotions” (4), portraying undeveloped communication skills and physical symptoms such as headaches, tension and stomach problems.
3. “Narcissists are usually charming and seductive characters ... are prone to rash, self aggrandising decisions ... divide the world into those who are either for or against them, casting the latter as villains” (deVries 3).

4. The leader with a bipolar disorder seems to have no emotional equilibrium. Because of their mood swings, their colleagues tend to have the impression they are constantly putting out emotional flare-ups. On the other hand, when they are on a high, they can draw others through their enthusiasm and winsome personality.

Winter says that these four personality disorders present one of the most complex aspects that define abusive leaders. The personality disorders become more complex when one considers the role that a person's childhood plays; often they are intertwined with the development of personality. It is difficult to approach a leader with the suggestion or accusation that the symptoms have been identified. At the same time, the presence of these personality disorders in leaders, and the unrecognized and therefore unresolved negative effects of their past, can result in disruption in organizations and irreparable damage in the victims (115).

2.3.4 Lack of Clarity

Lack of clarity is an organization-related aspect that relates to abusive leadership. In John Stackhouse's article on *Misplaced Metaphors Muddling Mission*, he poses the question: "Why do people who are fully capable professionals become weirdly dysfunctional when they participate in a Christian ministry?" (Stackhouse 62). He claims that, whereas businesses have a clear mandate and the employees have a fairly clear concept as to why they are there, people come to Christian organizations for a variety of reasons and different goals. Christian organizations are so complex that they become dysfunctional, lacking clarity and a sense of common goals and purpose. Hay claims that "Positive relationships abound around a strong sense of connection to the core mission" (2). The challenge that Christian organizations face lies in a leader having the capability and capacity to hear and understand the reasons and goals that the colleagues have for joining the organization and to clearly formulate and communicate the mandate so that all have a clear concept as to the direction the organization is moving and how the goals will be reached.

2.3.5 Powerseekers

According to Kessler, a leader should "never strive for power as an end in itself" (548). The powerseeker is one who practices the opposite of this ethical guideline. Lovas, the Norwegian missionary, preacher and founder of the Retreat Center Sandom further describes these Wolves in Sheep's Clothing as being obsessed with the need to dominate (16). Powerseekers are characterized in

the following ways. First of all, they are generally intelligent, winsome, and can be friendly, charming and flattering. Secondly, according to James 3:16 (16-17) these people are guilty of envy, selfishness and false ambitions leading to strife and disorder. Powerseekers desire to be seen in important places, to be honoured and greeted, as Jesus described the Pharisees in Matthew 23:5-7. Furthermore, the power-seeking leader has an aggressive mindset to the point of having one-sided, imbalanced opinions, blocking the supposed opponent, reducing self-confidence and self-esteem. Lovas also claims that “powerseekers are dangerous for churches when it comes to financial issues” (34).

Powerseekers are good speakers and debaters and can be convincing on issues, leading to bad decisions that involve finances. Furthermore, Lovas describes the powerseeker as having unrealistic expectations from those around them, making people feel guilty if they do not fulfil these unrealistic, ever changing expectations. Finally, they may misinterpret the Bible according to their needs. The previous subsections that discuss the aspects that define abusive leaders focus on the abusive leaders as individuals facing temptations, struggling in moral character, perhaps exhibiting personality disorders and seeking power.

2.3.6 Insecurity

Insecurity is another organization-related aspect that relates to abusive leadership. McClung, Jr. addresses the sensitive issue of the use and abuse of authority in Christian organizations. He states that it is important for organizations to be aware that “good but sometimes immature leaders can respond to selfish or needy people with overbearing authority, and ... cult figures can have so much influence on unwary young people, it is important to be aware of some of the unhealthy extremes leaders can go to in exercising their authority” (McClung, n.pg). He lists examples such as not feeling a need for accountability or submission, exalting themselves as authority figures (to a point that God never intended). Although we should point out abuses of authority, we should also recognize that becoming a wise leader requires years of experience, experience which includes mistakes and failures. Scripture gives many examples of failure on the part of those who went on to be greatly used by God, including Moses, Abraham, Jacob, Joseph, David, Peter, Paul, and many others (5). In an article, *10 Signs A Leader Is Insecure*, Christian psychologist, Dr. Evan Parks, links insecurity in a leader to misusing the authority that s/he has. The leader may present him/herself as being confident and sure, and is usually loving, helpful and good-natured. However, because of the insecurity the person feels easily threatened, is sensitive to criticism, and does not like to be questioned about the decisions that s/he makes. As a

result, the leader makes the lives of others difficult and is inflexible in solving problems. The leader makes hard decisions, does not allow others to contribute, and will even decide to close effective programs (quoted by Ndonye 23). The abuse is further evident by attempting to control every aspect of the organization, not allowing others to run their own departments. Parks observes that healthy leaders expect problems and can solve them, but an insecure leader will become angry when confronted with problems and setbacks (24). This is due to the fact that the insecure leader needs to be successful and be legitimized by others.

According to Winter, “The problem in the issue of insecurity lies in the fact that organizations may fill leadership positions with persons who feel insecure because of a lack of experience and/or training in leadership. The leaders may even lack the leadership gifts. These issues lead to insecurity and the resulting reaction described in this subsection” (36). The aspects that define abusive leaders discussed here help to create a clear description of how one could identify a leader who abuses his/her power. However, not all attributes can be found in one specific leader or organization. However, it is necessary to identify patterns in leaders in order to identify the abuse of power in the early phases of abusive processes.

2.4 Nature of the Victims of Abuse of Power

The discussion on the nature of the victims of abuse of power centres on the most vulnerable to become a victim and that is followed by a summary of eight factors that contribute to abuse, especially in Christian organizations according to Kessler and Kessler.

2.4.1 The Most Vulnerable to Become a Victim

First, it should be noted that, it takes two sides to set up a power-system: the abuser and the victims who allow themselves to be misused. Rather than risking the resistance and rejection in reproaching an abusive leader, the victims often choose to suffer or leave. Secondly, another aspect lies in the fact that people who are employed in Christian organizations tend to have high expectations of their leaders and the values that they express through their words and actions. As a result, abuse in these organizations is even more shocking and devastating for the employees, as it is coupled with deep disappointment. These high expectations are coupled with a sense of respect and trust in the leaders, and, as in the illustration, if the potential victim is conscientious, s/he may not trust him/herself to question the leader,

choosing to submit to the leader. Thirdly, personality and character traits define the victims of abuse (Kessler and Kessler 78).

Kessler and Kessler argue that a person's likelihood of becoming a victim is tied to their personality traits. Some individuals become victims due to their role in the power system, with the level of suffering being a key factor. Common traits of victims include submissiveness, a desire for harmony, guilt, and an inferiority complex. Victims are often sensitive, seek approval, and are concerned about others' opinions. They may show devotion to a leader, sacrificing their own needs to support them. Victims are often dramatic, led by emotions and relationships, and are easily manipulated by praise or its absence.

2.4.2 Eight Reasons for Power-seekers Influence

Kessler and Kessler determined the following eight reasons why it is so easy for powerseekers to be influential, especially in Christian organizations:

1. Spiritual leaders have power and wherever there is power there is the potential for abuse.
2. Some Christians do not believe that abuse can take place in Christian organizations.
3. Abuse does not fit into the moral Christian standards, resulting in the ignoring of any abusive situations.
4. Many Christians have a view of humility that is conducive to abuse.
5. Christians have an exaggerated need for harmony, resulting in difficulties in problem solving.
6. Leadership structures in many Christian organizations are not clearly defined.
7. Leaders in Christian organizations can claim the spiritual authority given to them by God, and can therefore not be questioned.
8. Christian organizations attract unstable personalities looking for leaders that they can look up to, resulting in unwanted abuse (Kessler and Kessler 41-42).

Winter commenting on the above pointed thus, “It is important to underline the main reasons that directly relate to victims and the reasons why they allow themselves to be abused, especially in Christian organizations. First of all, if Christians do not believe that abuse can take place in Christian

organizations, it will be easier to fall into the trap of a powerseeker and to fail to identify that an abusive process has begun. This is closely linked to the fact that abuse and moral Christian standards do not fit together, again, resulting in ignoring or not recognizing abusive processes. Christians may have the view that humility means that one does not question the leader. This may also be linked to the next reason, in that Christians need harmony and avoid conflicts that result when addressing an abusive leader. If people in organizations have unstable personalities, they will seek to be devoted to the leader. A powerseeker would readily take advantage of this type of person” (38). Although it is not likely that all of these reasons and all the aspects that define victims of abuse would be evident in one individual incident of the abuse of power in a Christian organization, patterns can be recognized. It reveals the necessity for leaders and their colleagues to become aware of the pitfalls and weaknesses that nourish the processes of the abuse of power in Christian organizations (Kessler and Kessler 43).

2.5 The Effects of Abuse of Power

When power is abused in Christian organizations, people are personally affected, even psychologically wounded. Organizations also suffer short- and long-term effects during and following an abusive process. Leaders of organizations must realize that there are personal and organizational results that need to be dealt with when power is abused. In the sub-section below the personal effects of the abuse of power from David Johnson and Jeff van Vonderen are discussed. This is followed by a brief discussion on the organizational results of the abuse of power.

2.5.1 Personal Effects

Actually, people who have become victims of the abuse of power in Christian organizations suffer on a personal level. The following areas of struggle resulting from the abuse of power have been identified by Johnson and van Vonderen (41-50):

- i. The victim develops a distorted image of God. This could result in feeling that God is never satisfied with what one achieves, is apathetic and does not help when people are hurt and abused and does not challenge the authority figure or organization. As well, the victim may feel that God is powerless to help when people are abused and hurting.
- ii. The victim may be preoccupied with spiritual performance, which leads to anxiety and shame. “In spiritual systems where performance is more important than emotional honesty or human need, both extremes will be strongly in evidence” (Johnson & van Vonderen 44).

- iii. The victim may have a distorted self-identity of him/herself as a Christian, a negative self-image or s/he may be confused with guilt and shame. The person has a negative identity as a Christian that can only be solved by good behavior.
- iv. The victim may have a problem relating to authority in a Christian organization. The victim often develops methods to protect him/herself from further abuse, leading to compliance or defiance, both of which do not offer protection, according to the authors.
- v. The victim may struggle with the concept of grace because of the shame s/he feels, leading to the sense of owing others when treated well.
- vi. The victim may struggle with setting personal boundaries when others demand responses and action from him/her. There is a feeling of shame for having an opinion and a struggle not to feel that one is selfish by wanting a right not to be abused.
- vii. The victim may have problems with personal responsibility because the person has experienced that no level of performance brings the desired, necessary and appropriate response and approval, leading to lethargy. At the same time, the victim may react in the other extreme and feel that he/she must resolve all problems and be responsible for every need or request.
- viii. The victim may lack living skills to be able to function outside of certain organizations or situations and is introverted and isolated.
- ix. The victim may have difficulty admitting the abuse, feeling that s/he is the problem, and exposing the abuse, even personally, creates feelings of disloyalty to the organization. The abuse begins to feel normal, and the victim fears that s/he is overreacting. Denial is a further factor, as the victim often cannot fathom that the abuse is actually taking place. When the victim is released from the abusive situation, s/he will see the situation more clearly (which leads to shame over having allowed oneself to be drawn into the situation).
- x. The victim may have difficulty trusting again. Twain once mused, “A cat that sits on a hot stove lid won’t ever sit on a hot stove lid again. But it probably won’t sit on a cold stove lid either”. Those who have been spiritually abused will have a hard time trusting a spiritual system again. This is extremely significant, because the essence of living as a Christian is a trust relationship with God, within God’s family (50).

The researcher followed Winter's discussion on the above to summarize the theme of these ten areas of struggle. It can be said that the victims can lose their trust in other Christians. They can also lose their trust in God, due to the fact that they feel that God did not resolve the problem and allowed abusive leaders to succeed in spite of the abusive behaviour. The victims can have feelings that swing between guilt for having allowed the abuse on the one hand, and, on the other hand, anger towards the perpetrator (Winter 40). The victim is in conflict, feeling a need to expose the abusive behavior in an organization, but, on the other hand, feeling a sense of responsibility to protect the organization. The victim feels like giving up and withdrawing, because of a feeling that no level of performance is sufficient. Finally, there is a struggle between complying and defying the system. This is truly a bleak description of a deeply wounded person.

Oakley claims that the abuse of power in Christian organizations has a long-term impact on individuals, due to the fact that there is a "lack of acceptance and recognition by others of the experience of it" (68). Christians may distance themselves from the victim because they feel uncomfortable with the stories. They have difficulty perceiving a Christian environment as unsafe. People are also unknowledgeable as to how to intervene and support the victims, and, as a result, the victims feel misunderstood and rejected.

2.5.2 Organizational Effects

Organizations also suffer from the effects of abusive processes. During the theoretical research process, it became evident to me that the documentation on the personal effects of the abuse of power in Christian organizations outweighs the documentation on the effects that the abuse of power has on organizations. Vredenburg and Brender clearly portrayed the process of the abuse of power in an organizational, hierarchical structure in subsection 2.2.2.4. Stackhouse refers to the uniqueness of Christian organizations (as found in subsection 2.3.4 above). One of the tragic effects of the abuse of power is the attrition of valuable workers. This has far-reaching results because skills and organizational knowledge are lost when people leave. If the perpetrators are not removed, the organization experiences repeated cycles of the abusive process, attrition and tension in the organization. This has far-reaching results because time and energy are utilized for the wrong issues. This results in financial slumps due to the fact that the contact with donors and friends of the organization is less intense. The organizational focus is distorted and there is a lack of clarity within and outside the organization.

The personal and organizational effects of the abuse of power in Christian organizations present challenges for healing processes and can leave permanent scars. Experiencing abusive behaviour influences the victim's spiritual condition and hinders the effectiveness of the organization.

2.6 Differentiating Power and Authority

In Christian setting, the terms “authority and power” are sometimes used interchangeably. Thus, it is imperative to define these terms, distinguish the differences between them, and explain why the researcher has chosen to use the term “power” in this research. Beasley-Murray defines “power” as “the means by which the leader actionably gains the compliance of the follower(s)” (109). May offers another definition of power, that it is the “the ability to cause or prevent change” (99). Oswald also states “that power relates to individuals’ ability to accomplish things outside or above the authority given to them in roles” (7). All the action verbs (compliance, cause, prevent, accomplish) in the three definitions appear with frequency. This means that the idea of action is central to the understanding of power. In these verbs, moreover, the idea of duress is implied. The term “power” is defined as it relates to this research as the leaders’ ability to get followers do those things, which bring God glory, and enhance both their temporal and eternal welfare. What makes power usage in the church context particularly complex and risky is the potential for leaders to wield it as if it is entirely their divine right to do so. Thus, the simple meaning of the term “power”, is exertion of pressure or influence on subordinates, so that a desired result is achieved.

Kessler and Winter define power and authority using Greek terms from the New Testament. *Dynamis* means ability or force, while *exousia* refers to permission or legitimating to do something. They argue that authority and power should go hand in hand. Weber defines power as the probability of carrying out one's will despite resistance, while Coleman explains the difference between power and authority: power is tied to personal characteristics, while authority is linked to social positions and roles. Authority must be consensual and legitimized, with the expectation of obedience.

Weber, a German sociologist, is well known for his definitions of power and authority. He defines power as “the probability that one actor within a social relationship will be in a position to carry out his own will despite resistance, regardless of the basis on which this probability rests” (53). Coleman, in his article on authority and power in leadership, presents Weber's comparison of these two terms, saying that, whereas power is associated with “personal characteristics of individuals or groups” (31), authority is associated with “social positions and roles” (31). In contrast to power, authority must be

consensual and legitimized, and the “right to command (and the probability of obedience) exists as a settled mutual expectation” (32).

For Coleman, authority legitimizes leaders to exercise the power that they have within a defined boundary. Power, on the other hand, can be exercised without direct engagement or involvement in decision-making by influencing processes “behind the scenes” (42). For the purpose of this research, the researcher chose to use the term “power” in order to maintain the advantage of studying its use and abuse in Christian leadership independently from examining the aspects that would be associated with the boundaries of authority leaders may have been given to exercise their power, and whether these boundaries were ignored.

By examining the abuse of power rather than authority, it is possible to collect information from leaders who may see themselves as the victims of abuse from their subordinates. In using the term “power,” the researcher is examining how Christian leaders use or abuse that which they are capable or have the ability to do. Because the term “power” is a central theme of this research, the researcher has constructed the following definition of power as it relates to a Christian leader in a Christian leadership: Power is the probability and ability that a Christian leader has to be positively or negatively influential in the system that he/she leads. The positive influence should result in the empowerment of others to accomplish effectively the task(s) for which the leadership exists.

2.7 Concept of Leadership

Over time, many have come up with varying definitions as it affects their perception of what leadership really connotes. Leadership is a concept that suggests direction, directorship, governorship, governance, administration, jurisdiction, captaincy, control, superintendence, ascendancy, rule, command, power, mastery, domination, dominion, premiership, and sovereignty. A leader is a person in authority that takes decision for an organization (Newman 2). According to Chand, "Leadership is an art whereby an individual influences a group of individuals for achieving a common set of goals: whose end must be reached when sets of rules are followed" (quoted by Janiver and Thaba 45). This implies that there is a rule which guides leadership to which leaders must possess if they must make impact in their leadership. It is a process whereby an individual influences a group of individuals to achieve a common goal. Leadership is about inspiring others to pursue your vision within the parameters you set, to the extent that it becomes a shared effort, a shared vision, and a shared success (Mill 13).

Note that the definitions above have a couple of processes in common: A person influences others through social influence, not power; to get something accomplished (bosses use power to get things done). Leadership requires others, who are not necessarily direct-reports, to get something accomplished. There is a need to accomplish something. Leaders carry out this process by applying their leadership knowledge and skills. Leaders carry out this process by applying their leadership knowledge and skills (Uhl-Bien 655).

Kruse, attempting to define leadership in his article quotes the definitions of respected professionals, beginning with Peter Drucker, who claims that a leader is someone who has followers. Warren Bennis says: “Leadership is the capacity to translate vision into reality.” Bill Gates claims: “As we look ahead into the next century, leaders will be those who empower others”. John Maxwell writes: “Leadership is influence – nothing more, nothing less”. After carefully analyzing these definitions, Kruse defines leadership as “a process of social influence, which maximizes the efforts of others, toward the achievement of a goal” (Kruse 1). The researcher considers Kruse’s definition appropriate for good leadership, but would pose the question: What if the efforts of others are not made best use of and/or the goal is not realized – is that no longer leadership? Furthermore, who will define whether the efforts of others are utilized properly or not? What if the wrong goals are followed?

DePree complements the definition by saying that leadership “is an art, something to be learned over time, not simply by reading books. Leadership is more tribal than scientific, more a weaving of relationships than an amassing of information” (2). The art of leadership means “liberating people to do what is required of them in the most effective and humane way possible” (DePree 1), and that “to be a leader means, especially, having the opportunity to make a meaningful difference in the lives of those who permit leaders to lead” (22). Peter Northouse’s concise definition of leadership is most appropriate for this dissertation. He defines leadership as “a process whereby an individual influences a group of individuals to achieve a common goal” (Northouse6). Northouse’s definition underlines four components of leadership: Process, influence, groups and common goals. Leadership as a process is a transaction that occurs between the leader and the followers, resulting in interaction rather than a linear process. Wessels takes this interaction a step further, stating that leadership “has to do with connecting with people and communicating with them on a deep level ... It is much more than good communication; it is leadership that connects with followers on a deep level of understanding. It is leadership which shows maturity and sincerity” (485).

Thus, everyone participates in the leadership process. Leadership as an influence has to do with how the leader affects followers, and is crucial in order for leadership to take place. The third component of leadership is groups, and without groups that have a common purpose, independent of the size, leadership cannot take place. The fourth component is having common goals to achieve. Northouse explains that this fourth component of mutuality “lessens the possibility that leaders might act toward followers in ways that are forced or unethical” (6). He continues to say that “leaders have an ethical responsibility to attend to the needs and concerns of followers” (7). They are not above the followers, nor are they better. The key to Northouse’s approach to leadership lies in an understanding between leaders and followers in “leadership relation” (7) to each other.

Greenleaf maintains that leadership is the relationship in which one person or the leader influence others to work together willingly on related task to attain that which a leader desire. He further posit that leadership is the ability of management to induce sub ordinance to work towards group goals with confidence and keenness (2). This implies that the leader accepts responsibility for the achievement of the group objective and it is therefore essential for the trust and co-operation from both sides to be evidence all the time. Base on this, one can rightly say that leadership is an art of getting things done. It can be learnt, improved, developed and perfected. It is a process of influence and the process always includes a number of key components such as: - leaders and followers, as they interact.

According to Iroegbu, leadership is the responsibility of conducting a people or group towards the achievement of determined goals. It entails being in-charge, as well as having the power to direct the affairs of such people to arrive at expected results (246). Leadership is also seen as the act of showing way for others, stating the goal and thereby giving certainty and purpose to others who may have difficulty in achieving it for themselves. (15). Kelling opines that leadership is services, since it seeks to meet the need of another or the group by performing needed function (13). This connotes the process of guiding, directing and commanding others to achieve a desired goal or vision.

2.8 Ethical Theories of Leadership

Northouse suggests, “ethical theories are about both the actions of leaders and who they are as people” (343). Consequently, there are two major domains of ethical leadership: “theories about leaders’ conduct and theories about leaders’ character” (344).

2.8.1 Theories on the Conduct of a Leader

According to the first domain, the conduct of a leader is determined by either the consequences of his/her actions or decisions or by a moral obligation to do what is right. Therefore, the conduct of the leader is either teleological or deontological in nature. The teleological approach includes the possibility that the actions of a leader can fall into the realm of ethical egoism, utilitarianism, or altruism. In other words, even though the morality of a leader's conduct is determined by the outcome of his/her actions, the outcome is molded by the motivation for the actions. That motivation is the greatest good for himself/herself (ethical egoism), the greatest good for the greatest number (utilitarianism), or the greatest good for others (ethical altruism) (Northouse 344).

Utilitarianism is a normative moral theory based on the principle of utility or usefulness of an action. Jeremy Bentham and John Stuart Mill proposed that its goal (*telos*) is the greatest happiness for the greatest number. According to the utilitarian view, "actions are right or wrong depending upon whether or not they further progress toward an end (*telos*) or goal that is worth striving for . . . The ends, or consequences, justify the means you choose" (119). All teleological approaches are based on the principle of utility, but they are differentiated by who benefits from that utility (myself, others, or the greatest number).

Although Christianity is concerned with the ultimate end—the kingdom of God—for Christians, that end alone is not a justification for the use of bad means in the process of achieving that goal. Stassen and Gushee expressed the Christian view on ethics: We believe a Jesus-centered ethic takes divine commands seriously and is indeed vigorously deontological. But it understands the mandates and teachings of Jesus to be gracious and authoritative instructions concerning how to do the will of God (deontological) and how to participate in the coming of the kingdom of God (teleological) (121).

Reconciling the prevalent pragmatic and utilitarian use of power, which includes many abuses of power in today's political and business world, with the Christian ideals of love and sacrifice is almost impossible. Unfortunately, many politicians, businessmen, and sometimes, even Christian leaders try to apply them together. The deontological moral theory regards the actions of leaders as morally correct if they fulfill their duty to do what is right despite the consequences. It studies the relationship between duty and morality. Immanuel Kant derives his arguments for deontological ethics from human reason and defines the ultimate good as follows: "There is nothing it is possible to think of anywhere in the

world, or indeed anything at all outside it, that can be held to be good without limitation, excepting only a good will” (Kant 9)

Kant proposes the existence of an intrinsic goodness regardless of the ultimate end. He says, “The good will is good not through what it effects or accomplishes, not through its efficacy for attaining any intended end, but only through its willing, i.e., good in itself, and considered for itself. . .” (10.) Based on deontological ethics, an action is morally good because of the intrinsic goodness of the action itself. Whether the product of an action is good is irrelevant. Motives make an action wrong or right. Thereby, deontological ethics is primarily concerned with intentions and motives. Kant defines that obligation to follow duties as the categorical imperative: “The categorical imperative is thus only a single one, and specifically this: *Act only in accordance with that maxim through which you can at the same time will that it become a universal law*” (37). Consequently, the actions of leaders depend on their understanding of what is right. Therefore, the ultimate goal of a leader is to behave according to principle, regardless of the final result. Such a perspective focuses on the actions of leaders and their obligation to do what is right.

2.8.2 Theories on the Character of a Leader

The second domain of ethical leadership is concerned with the character of the leader. It is not limited to a leader’s behavior in public discourse, but is also concerned with the inherent complexity of attributes that determines a person’s moral and ethical actions. Those theories are virtue-based theories and are concerned with who leaders are as persons. Al Gini asserts, “the quality of leadership can be measured only by what a leader intends, values, or stands for—in other words, by character. In *Character: America’s Search for Leadership*, Gail Sheehy argues, as did Aristotle before her that “character is the most crucial and most elusive element of leadership” (Gini 162).

Virtue ethics is a moral theory that emphasizes the role of virtue and character rather than the consequence of the act or duty. It is teleological in nature because it is concerned with the ultimate goal and purpose of life, while differing from utilitarianism, which emphasizes the goal as a justification of the means. Virtue ethics instead emphasizes the means to achieve those goals—virtues—and how they shape character, and ultimately who we are. Durant describes Aristotle’s ethics: “We are what we repeatedly do” (61). Actions matter and they define us (Aristotle 4). According to Aristotle, virtue is the most important means of achieving happiness. Virtues are a pathway to happiness—the “ultimate” good. They are not the goal, but the means. As Durant comments: “we do not act rightly because we

have virtue or excellence, but we rather have these because we have acted rightly” (61). The difference among us is what we consider to be good, and what we believe will bring us happiness. As Morris quoting Pascal asserted:

All men seek happiness. This is without exception. Whatever different means they employ, they all tend to this end. The cause of some going to war, and of others avoiding it, is the same desire in both, attended with different views. The will never takes the least step but to this object. This is the motive of every action of every man, even of those who hang themselves (97).

Motives are crucial aspects of power use that are typically not obvious. Although leaders typically conceal them behind secondary reasons (or excuses), they determine the direction and type of leadership leaders will apply. An analysis of power abuse attempts to recognize motives to determine when such abuse occurred.

Another important notion of virtue ethics related to the issue of power is the principle of the golden mean between two extremes. “According to Aristotle, virtue is a mean between two extremes, both of which are vices—either excess or deficiency (or defect)” (Thiroux 65). That mean is not the mathematical mean between two extremes, but a moral choice that requires wisdom to do what is right. According to Plantak, this implies that a virtuous leader will do what is right, apply the right amount and type of power in his/her leadership, and avoid vices, that is, abuses that can be excessive or deficient, including the extreme use of power, or not using power when it is needed (54).

Virtue ethics applied in Christian leadership goes beyond what is visible. We are what we are, not only when making decisions and acting in a manner that is visible to all, when it can benefit us personally, or when it is in the best interest of others, but also when nobody sees us and when there is no visible benefit or reward for our decisions or behavior. The power of a leader is affected by his/her position, decisions, and actions, and also by his/her personality and who he/she is. Although the leader’s character is unimportant in some leadership positions, in the realm of Christian leadership, it is of essential importance (Gini 162). A Christian leader cares about traits of his character and cherishes Christian virtues. Ignoring those virtues or being corrupted by vices is an abuse of power.

2.8.3 Principle-centered Leadership

In addition to theories on the conduct and character of leaders, Covey introduced “principle-centered leadership.” “Principle-centered leadership introduces a new paradigm—that we center our lives and

our leadership of organizations and people on certain ‘true north’ principles” (19). Our leadership is determined by the principles we follow. They shape our priorities, methods, decisions, our conduct, and character.

Therefore, a distinction among leaders can be made based on how well they apply true principles in their leadership. Covey suggested some universal and self-evident principles to follow and apply to leadership. “Our effectiveness is predicated upon certain inviolate principles—natural laws in the human dimension that are just as real, just as unchanging, as laws such as gravity are in the physical dimension” (18). Covey named those principles as fairness, equity, justice, integrity, honesty, and trust. Furthermore, he indicated,

Principles are not invented by us or by society; they are the laws of the universe that pertain to human relationships and human organizations. They are part of the human condition, consciousness, and conscience;” and “Principles are self-evident, self-validating natural laws. They do not change or shift. Principles apply at all times in all places. They surface in the form of values, ideas, norms, and teachings that uplift, ennoble, fulfill, empower, and inspire people. The lesson of history is that to the degree people and civilizations have operated in harmony with correct principles, they have prospered (18-19).

Even though the existence of those principles is observable, the problem is that their interpretation and definition is highly affected by culture, society, beliefs, and ideology. A lack of universal agreement about “true north” principles is an obvious problem. According to Christianity, the “true north” principle would be following the teaching of Scripture and the example of the incarnate God, Jesus Christ.

Covey proposed that the best approach in the assessment of principle-centered leadership is to examine why people follow leaders (18). According to this measurement, he suggests three types of leadership that may be differentiated by the type of power leaders have over followers: coercive power, utility power, and legitimate power. This division has obvious similarities to the previously mentioned types of power: power over, power within, and power with. On the level of coercive power, individuals follow out of fear. When utility power is exercised, individuals follow because they expect some personal benefit from following the leader. A third type is based on the trust and rightful authority leaders possess. Their followers are committed, trusting, and hold them in the highest respect (Plantak 58). From the ethical perspective, leadership that is based on legitimate power is the most desired type

of leadership because it is based on positive motivation and stimulation rather than on fear or selfish interest. Legitimate power is related to the character and conduct of the leader.

2.9 Concept of Christian Leadership

A Christian leader influences others not by the powers of his own personality but his personality is influenced and empowered by the Holy Spirit. A spiritual leader comes by the anointing, it can never be self-generated. He is able to influence others spirituality only because the spirit is able to work in and through him to a greater degree than in those whom he leads. A Christian leader seeks to find God's will. Unlike a natural leader who enjoys commanding others, a spiritual leader's delight is to obey God. He is motivated by love for God and man (Hagher 22).

Leadership in the church is believed to be a call. Often, the awareness of the call is coupled with fear of personal inadequacies that one is too weak to be a strong leader. Hence, every leader needs to depend on God for effective leadership ability. McCain said that, change the leader and you will change the organization (18). Thus, organization success and failures are dependent on leadership. Unchanged leaders are equal to unchanged organization. Lingenfelter concur on the fact that if you want to continue leading, you must continue changing. To be a leader, one must prepare all through his life the attitude of being receptive to new ideas (*Transforming Culture* 17). The quality of leadership one gives depends upon one's ability to bring new ideas and to embrace changes for the sake of the followers. When a leader resists change, he resists progress. People often resist change when an idea is not self-initiated. Terry, speaking on Church leadership posited that the Bible has always been a guide to Christian leaders. This is also supported by Akanni who stated that a Christian leader must be one who sees ahead of all others. He knows where he is going and the way to it. He has a vision of what to do and how to do it. After all explanations, he can confidently say, "follow me, this is the way I will make you get to the desire of your heart" (32). A Christian leader must be a man of vision; a man endowed with the ability to influence or lead others to God. He is patient with the sluggish and explains again and again. He uses various means to avoid unhealthy monopoly. He depends on the Holy Spirit to convince, convict and convert men. He leads by converting people from within to become one with the vision just like himself.

Myles said that Christian leadership is about influence and not control; it is not considering your interest and decision as a leader without considering the interest and decision of your followers (23), and such understanding is better made considering McCain's definition that Christian leadership is a

kind of leadership that provides positive influence for others. He says, a Christian leader is the one who has led himself effectively and served as an ethical, moral effective example for others. He leads with humility, compassion, has mastered the art of forgiveness and can be a child when need be.

Mamman affirmed in his opinion that, at the heart of Christian leadership is Christ's revolutionary idea of a leader as the servant of all, and service to humanity as the hall-mark of greatness. He said, Christian leadership is modelled after Christ who said; "I am the good shepherd" (n.pg). The responsibilities of a shepherd include; loving and caring for his flock, lead them to greener pasture and guard and protect his flock from danger. He cited Isara who summarized Jesus' idea in these words: "the ministry of Jesus is interpreted in the context of servant-hood and summed up in total and unparalleled service. Jesus' entire work and death are described in service. Mark 10:43 emphasizes the greatness of servant-hood which culminate in the life of Jesus" (4). Jesus is the model of humble service in contrast to the hunger for power and domination in the world.

The researcher saw the opinion of Mamman to be true as Christ is a model for Christian leaders to follow at all time and in all things. Having Mamman's opinion in mind, Fiedler sees a Christian leader as one who has a divine mandate to take others to a particular place or to achieve a particular aim. He teaches, corrects, rebukes and disciplines as long as the purpose of leadership is achieved. His sole aim of ever-leading should be to obey the mandate of God and achieve desired goals. The definitions stated above of who a Christian leader is, point to the fact that a Christian leader is the one that is called by God into leadership. He is the one that yield himself to the leadership of the Holy Spirit in his leadership. He is the servant of all, called to serve and not to be served.

Blackaby rightly noted that "spiritual leadership is not an occupation: it is a calling" (11). They further state that holding a leadership position in a Christian organization does not make one a spiritual leader neither does working in a secular occupation preclude one from being a spiritual leader at the workplace. These sentiments echo what Malphurs too has concluded, that: "a Christian leader leads in any context whether or not it's a professed Christian organization. Christian leaders are leaders outside of as well as inside the Christian community. Our mandate is to lead in a Christian way regardless of the context" (13). In the same light, experienced leaders acknowledge that knowledge and skills will only get one so far. If a leader is not in good shape in their soul, their ministry will soon end up in frustration or disaster (Lewis, n.pg).

In highlighting the crucial role leaders play in shaping out their circumstances, Lingenfelter observes that in the universal church, independent power exclusively belongs to the Lord Jesus Christ, but he has delegated authority to church leaders, and the process leaders employ to confer that authority grows out of the prevailing social environment (*Leading Cross-culturally* 81). In the same light, that church growth is uniquely and intimately tied to leadership – both pastoral and lay. Church leaders who make the most lasting contributions to God’s kingdom are those who eschew the world’s standards and patterns and lead through the biblical model of servanthood (Smith 28). The servant pattern consists of living, leading, and acting on behalf of others. The servant pattern refuses to manipulate, coerce, or force and its central purpose remains the benefit of the served.

2.9.1 Ethics in Christian Leadership

“Ethics is critical reflection on the moral norms, values and behaviour of individuals and societies in order to assess their validity ... an analysis of and a deliberate reflection on moral judgments, actions and lifestyle” (Kretzschmar 16). Christian ethics reflects on questions relating to a good life, a good person, what is the right, good and wise way to live, how we live with others and react to issues in the world. Applied to the framework of leadership, one could ask “What is an ethical leader?”; “What is the right, good and wise way to lead?”; “How do we work with others and react to issues in the organization?” Plueddemann defines good, ethical Christian leaders: “Good leaders are fervent disciples of Jesus Christ, gifted by the Holy Spirit, with a passion to bring glory to God. They use their gift of leadership by taking the initiative to focus, harmonize and enhance the gifts of others for the sake of developing people and cultivating the kingdom of God” (15). Whereas “leaders are people who are able to inspire, encourage and guide others” (Kretzschmar 47), ethical leaders are “trustworthy persons of integrity and competence who encourage and enable others to develop moral character and achieve goals that are just and good” (47). In chapter 2 (sub-section 2.2.2) Vredenburg and Brender presented the hierarchical abuse of power. With regard to their assertion, they explained the ethics of hierarchical power, the first issue being the importance of respecting a subordinate’s human dignity, that people are valuable in themselves. A further ethical criterion is that of an individual’s rights to privacy, truthfulness and safety. Thirdly, organizations are endowed with power from society in return for their contributions to the good of society, expecting that the organizations will follow the community’s norms and laws. Lastly, preventing deserved rewards violates the ethics of fairness or justice. After considering these descriptions and definitions of ethical Christian leadership it is necessary to focus on what constitutes ethical Christian leadership.

2.9.2 Characteristics of Ethical Christian Leader

Schubert carried out a Christian-ethical dialogue between two groups of Christians to determine how they would prioritize five ethical values that both groups agreed are important for Christian leaders to practice. Although both groups could identify with the same values, the two groups prioritized the values in an almost perfect mirror image.

First Group: Justice, Faithfulness, Humility, Love and Mercy

Second Group: Love, Mercy, Humility, Faithfulness and Justice (183).

Schubert determined that “biblical values are strongly influenced by cultural values” (184). In the individualistic society, justice and faithfulness are highly valued, whereas in the communalistic, people-centered society, love and mercy are highly valued. Schubert also determined that the expression of each of the values is dependent on the cultural background of the individuals in the organization. Thus, it becomes challenging to lay out biblical values for ethical leadership that are understood and practiced by all individuals within and between cultures.

The five ethical values that are listed above are values related to inner character. Although many of the values that one would expect would define an ethical Christian leader are intertwined with each other, the researcher have chosen to focus on the values that relate not only to inner character, but also to the practical expression of character (for example the importance of being a servant, being fair and the willingness to be accountable).

i. Spiritual Transformation

Kretzschmar emphasizes the importance of spiritual transformation in the lives of Christian leaders:

Spiritual formation is indispensable for Christian leaders first because it results in a wider vision of reality and a deepened engagement with society. Second, it enables leaders to live the spiritual and moral vision of the Christian gospel. Third, it helps them to avoid moral and other pitfalls. Fourth, it helps leaders to open the gate to truth, for example, within psychological and business management studies of leadership. Finally, spiritual formation enables leaders increasingly to discern good and evil in the world and to reflect on their own ministries with greater honesty and discernment (Kretzschmar 3).

She goes on to state that the spiritual and moral maturity of leaders of Christian organizations cannot be over-emphasized. Personal transformation is a lifelong process that should take place as a result of an ongoing relationship with God, resulting in a change of thinking, living and leading. Spiritual formation is an inner journey (relationship with God and our true selves), a shared journey (in fellowship with other Christians), and an outer journey (reaching out to the world). Grün, a Benedictine Monk and financial administrator of a monastery, shares his experience on spiritual transformation in leaders. He believes that a leader must be prepared to change oneself. He/She must be self-reflective and capable of leading him/herself before being capable of leading others (13). Grün underlines the importance of integrating the virtues of humility, emotional self-control, fairness, decisiveness, modesty and frugality in one's lifestyle. This involves gaining wisdom through experience, becoming mature, giving up the fight for power and influence) and fearing God. In considering the attributes that define abusive leaders as discussed in chapter two, spiritual transformation in the lives of Christian leaders stands in contrast to the attributes that define abusive leaders (Winter 46). It is to be expected that a leader who has the ability for self-reflection and a desire to develop spiritually will be less tempted to abuse his/her power. This should result in fair and just treatment of all members in the team.

ii. Love

Love is an important aspect of ethical Christian leadership. As seen in the chart in 3.2.2 above, both the Western and Tanzanian participants prioritized love as an essential value, but with different prioritization. Kessler sets the foundation for the leadership principles by describing the twofold law of love from Mark 12:29-31, stating that, if love is the most important law for mankind, then love is also the most important law for Christian leaders (6).

The twofold law of love has a vertical dimension (loving God) and a horizontal dimension (loving others). Kessler makes it clear that this text does not say that we should love ourselves, but rather that it is assumed that if one loves him/herself in a normal, healthy, psychological manner, s/he will treat him/herself well, and should treat others in the same way. The twofold law of love is especially important for Christian leaders because they are role models for their followers. He defines a leader as a person whom others follow, and a Christian leader is one who consciously follows Christ, whether he leads in a Christian or secular organization. Kessler continues to explain leadership and love: "A person should never be entrusted with a leadership position if s/he does not love the people s/he is leading" (8).

The twofold law of love becomes practical through the important principles of leadership: service, power, accountability and forgiveness. Just as the twofold law of love has a vertical dimension and a horizontal dimension, these principles also have vertical and horizontal dimensions.

- I serve God, and I serve others.
- I have received power from God, and I have power over others.
- I am accountable to God and to others, and I am accountable for others who I lead.
- I live from God's forgiveness, and I am willing to forgive those with whom I work.

The second group of Christians that prioritized love as presented above would agree with Kessler: love is the top ingredient that determines how all other values and principles of ethical Christian leaders are played out. The first group of Christian leaders prioritized justice. Love and justice (or fairness) cannot be separated: if a Christian leader truly loves those with whom s/he works, treating them justly and fairly should be a natural consequence.

iii. Servant Leadership

A further aspect or value that should define ethical Christian leadership is service, as seen in Kessler's principles. Jesus addresses the topic of servant leadership, contrasting it with the attitude with which the rulers of that time lorded their authority over the Gentiles (Matthew 20:25-28). He makes it clear that those who want to lead must first be willing to serve and give their lives for others, treating others in a just, fair and equal manner. The "Servant Leadership Model" was presented to the business world by Robert Greenleaf (1904-1990) in 1970 when he wrote an essay entitled "The Servant as Leader". The model emphasizes the importance of serving others (employees, customers, and community) as the top priority. "Servant-leadership emphasizes increased service to others, a holistic approach to work, a sense of community, and shared decision-making power" (Spears 3-4). Spears explains that Greenleaf's model teaches that a conscious decision to serve first results in an aspiration to lead and to see persons grow, become healthier, wiser, independent, and becoming servants themselves.

Stahlke and Laughlin say that Servant Leadership means exhibiting leadership that empowers and not overpowers, exchanging oppression for freedom to excel, and fear of failure for being encouraged to take risks and being allowed to learn from making mistakes (233). Kretzschmar underlines these thoughts by using Christ's example of servant leadership (Mark 10:35-45). "He taught with authority but was never authoritarian, he was compassionate but never ineffectual, he was just but never judgmental" (Kretzschmar42). Kessler lists Servant Leadership as one of the most important principles

of leadership. “A good Christian leader serves God first, then the organization, and thirdly, the people in the organization” (Kessler 27). Normally these three directions of service fit together. However, if there is conflict, the leader is first and foremost responsible to God, then to the organizational task, and lastly to the colleagues who are helping to fulfil the mandate. A servant leader’s mandate is more important than his/her position, and the priority should be to serve and not to lead. Servant leaders must be capable of leading themselves, which requires maturity and self-discipline. Servant leaders must be open for criticism and correction, and be good listeners.

Balda and Balda question the use of the term Servant Leadership, saying that it has become a cliché that many have enthusiastically adopted without giving it much thought, specifically the implications of being a servant: being a ransom for many as Jesus was. They refer to Peter Drucker and his assertions that the manager serves the institution, not the employees, customers or shareholders. At the same time, “the manager can generate performance through good leadership, ethical behavior and affirming relationships with followers and subordinates; but the priorities must never be confused” (Balda and Balda 43). They conclude by suggesting that the “only true test for a so-called servant leader is a confidential reality check with the followers” (43). Followers will readily assess the status of servanthood in their leaders. Northouse claims: “When individuals engage in servant leadership, it is likely to improve outcomes at the individual, organization, and societal levels” (238).

iv. Accountability

Although accountability is considered to be negative in the eyes of some leaders, it is an important aspect of ethical Christian leadership, as seen in the following quote. Richelle Wiseman quotes John Pellowe, CEO of the Canadian Council of Christian Charities (CCCC): “What I feel acutely is that someday, as leader of a Christian organisation, I will be called into account not just for how I led the organisation, but also how I stewarded the people” (Wiseman 33). Accountability is necessary to maintain values of ethical Christian leadership. English literature tends to use the term “authority” in relationship to “accountability” with the intention of making leaders aware of the fact that they have been placed in positions and given the authority to use their power (independent of the base of that power) in their given position. This position of given authority to exercise power demands accountability, not only to those who have given the leader the authority, but also to those subordinates for whom the leader is responsible and to God. For example, Stahlke and Laughlin discuss accountability as an important and necessary factor that is closely connected to Servant Leadership.

They say that accountability “welcomes giving and receiving objective evaluation of working relationships and performance of self and others” (4329). Although the term accountability is actually neutral, it is often avoided because it is often thought of in negative terms.

Accountability has two purposes: 1) Monitoring: the authority and responsibility of a person or group and making necessary corrections. 2) Measuring: to determine whether or not the goals have been reached and standards were kept. Stahlke and Laughlin state: “We are always accountable to the person or group from whom our authority comes. We can delegate authority and we can delegate responsibility, but we can’t delegate accountability” (1034). Accountability leads to affirmation for delivering the expected results. At the same time, accountability includes addressing and removing destructive and dysfunctional behaviour, which exposes or removes the abuser. A lack of accountability of the leadership to those above him/her in the structure, or within a board or committee can harm healthy working relationships and lead to abuse.

Kessler also underlines the necessity of accountability, and considers it to be one of the four main principles of leadership. Because human beings receive their authority from God, it is impossible to have authority without accountability for the use of this God-given authority (53). Thus, accountability should result in reduced abuse of this authority. Because power comes from God, leaders are first and foremost accountable to God. Secondly, they are accountable to those who have given them the authority to exert their power in their leadership position. Finally, leaders are accountable for the way in which their decisions and actions influence other people. Thus, accountability structures in an organization should provide a platform for personal and interpersonal reflection that would reveal unfair or unjust behaviour by a leader. Max Weber sheds further light on theories of sovereign authority, in which a ruler believes that s/he has received his/her authority directly from God, and is, therefore, “responsible only to God” (Coleman 34) and not to colleagues, boards, or even subordinates. If a leader understands the line of accountability to be limited to God, and not to others, and the leader falsely claims the actions and decisions to be a mandate from God, the followers will be intimidated and hesitant to question the leader, because in doing so, they are made to feel that they are questioning God.

v. Trust and Forgiveness

Trust and forgiveness is a pair that cannot be separated. Regarding trust, Covey states that no matter how good the rhetoric or intentions of a leader are, without trust there will not be a basis for success

(785). “A key feature of effective leadership is the ability to be innovative in order to transform the group and steer it in new directions. Trust plays a central role in this process” (Hogg 1245). “Forgiveness is free, but trust is expensive” (Stahlke and Loughlin 1067). It is a value that is often misunderstood and mistaken for forgiveness, as trust must be earned by being found trustworthy on the basis of behaviour. One should be called to account for decisions and actions and be found trustworthy, but trust does not replace accountability. Trustworthiness leads to more trust. When the trust account carries a deficit, due to bad experiences, the result is a broken relationship that can only be rebuilt on behaviour worthy of trust, bringing the trust account in the positive. Trust is built on the basis of an accountability system through the negotiation of strategic and tactical goals, regular relationship reviews, documenting important communications, and replacing assumptions with agreements.

Regarding forgiveness, Kessler states that a Christian leader is one who is aware of the fact that he/she needs God’s forgiveness and his/her relationship to God is the basis for living (Kessler 65). Leaders who are aware of this, and can deal with their sinful nature through forgiveness from Jesus Christ do not need to find another person to carry blame for their own actions. It is important in Christian organizations to build a culture of forgiveness, so that when things go wrong people will acknowledge, admit and confess their shortcomings, and be forgiven, rather than trying to cover up their mistakes. If a leader can admit to having done wrong, it will help to create a culture in which the workers will also be more willing to forgive each other. If a leader can receive forgiveness, he/she will have the tolerance that is necessary to understand and forgive others.

2.10 Summary of Literature Review

From the literature review many work have been done on abuse of power but it is on organizational areas, not specifically in regards to the Church. The research gap of this thesis is based on some churches with abusive Christian leaders who take their congregants for granted. Research has only been done on the effects of abuse of power on the victims and the church but nothing has been researched in the area of the effects of abuse of power on the abusive church leaders themselves and the society where the church is situated. On the causes of abuse of power, few books have been written from a western perspective, but the books the researcher came across, nothing is explored from an African culture, especially about abuse of power in Christian leadership.

CHAPTER THREE

EXEGETICAL STUDY OF I SAMUEL 12:1-5

The researcher in this chapter handled the exegetical study of 1 Samuel 12:1-5 and ends with a theological conclusion.

3.1 Background of I Samuel 12:1-5

The books of first and second Samuel were originally one until the Hebrew Old Testament was translated into Greek and named Septuagint (Yakubu 9). The authorship of the book Samuel is a hot debate among scholars. Most scholars subscribe to anonymous authorship. Others claim Samuel authorship whose record of death in 1 Samuel 25 refuted (Delitzsch and Keil, n.pg). According to Jewish tradition the book was attributed to the prophet Samuel, with additions by the prophets Gad and Nathan (www.jewishencyclopedia.com), but modern scholars view it as a composition of a number of independent texts of various ages from c. 630–540 BCE (Halley 181). For Dickson, it covers a period of about 125 years probably from about 1140 to 1015 B.C (313). Generally, the books of Samuel deal with the establishment of kingship in Israel beginning from the termination of the age of the administration of the judges with Samuel as the last of the judges to the close of the reign of King David (Delitzsch and Keil, n.pg).

The book of I Samuel has the name “Samuel” in the title. McCain asserts that no one knows who wrote the books of 1 and 2 Samuel, though there is speculation that the original source was a prophet like Samuel, Nathan and Gad (159). The book may have been named after Samuel because it begins with a large account of him, his birth and childhood, his life and government, the history of the reigns of Saul and David, who were both anointed by him. In view of statements made in I Samuel 5:5; 6:18; 27:6, it seems that the book of Samuel was written after the reign of Solomon but before the Babylonian captivity. Thus, the date will be sometime between 931 BC, the time Israel divided into the Northern and Southern Kingdoms after the death of Solomon and 586 BC, the date of the Babylonian captivity of Judah, the southern kingdom of Israel (Dickson 314).

The book of I Samuel describes the crucial turning point in Israel's history from that of the judges to the rule of a king. The book sets forth the tension between the people's expectation of a king and God's pattern of a theocracy in which he was their King (Stamps 412). It treats the judgeship of Prophet Samuel and the reign of Saul, from his election to his rejection and the decline of his Kingdom during

his conflict with David, who the Lord had chosen to be king of his people in place of Saul (Keil and Delitzsch, n.pg). As Howard asserted, the questions of whether and how the monarchy should be established dominate the first portions of 1 Samuel. These are followed by the question of who should be the king of Israel, the coronation of the first king in Israel as well as the choice and the anointing of the second monarch (141).

The book of first Samuel marks a period of transition in the history of Israel. It was narrative from direct theocratic rule of God to his role to a king with the exhortation of the prophets. Because Samuel was old and his sons did not follow after the tradition of his spiritual leadership, the people sought for a king to whom they could transfer their allegiance and a centralized leader like other nations around them (Dickson 322). It could be said at this point that the Israelites shifted their sense of security from God to Man. God dealt with Israel in reference to many of the Israelites desires and send to Samuel to anoint a king for them called Saul, the son of Kish. Thus, summarily, one could divide the book into three sections: renewal under Samuel (1-7:17), the reign of Saul (8:1-15:35), Saul's decline and David's rise (16:1-31:13) (Cook, n.pg). Its major characters are Samuel, Saul and David.

3.2 Contexts of 1 Samuel 12:1-5

1 Samuel 12 is the twelfth chapter of the first book of Samuel in the Old Testament of the Christian Bible or the first part of the Books of Samuel in the Hebrew Bible (Halley 181). This chapter contains Samuel's address to the people of Israel after Saul's coronation (Knight 62). This is within a section comprising 1 Samuel 7–15 which records the rise of the monarchy in Israel and the account of the first years of King Saul (Jones 197). This chapter closes the period of the Israel Judges, concluding the cycle of alternative pro- and anti-monarchical strands. It began with an anti-monarchical stance of Samuel which is a repetition of statements in 8:1–22, but with a new element—a contrast between the old prophetic regime and the new royal one (Jones 199).

The twelve tribes had been governed by judges for nearly 500 years, but during the tenure, Israel demanded for monarchical rule suggesting a rejection of the kingship of Yahweh and the leadership of Samuel. God had directed Samuel to anoint Saul, the son of Kish, a Benjamite as king over Israel to which Samuel concurred. Samuel thus closed the confirmation of Saul as king over Israel with an address to all Israel. This chapter consists of the farewell speech of Samuel interspersed with the responses by the people (Oliver 112). It was organized at Gilgal. It appeared to be a public meeting where many Israelites were gathered probably celebrating the coronation of their desired king.

After stating that the kingship was a “concession in response to popular demand” (verse 1), Samuel admitted that this was a departure from the kind of leadership exercised by himself, and posed a number of questions with the aim of justifying his ruling thus far (Evans 134). The verb *'take'* became a key to compare his just leadership, as the prophet had *'taken'* nothing from the people, to the future *'ways of the king'* (1 Samuel 8:11-18), where a number of things will be *'taken'* from the people by the king, therefore the people had taken a step backwards in requesting for a king (Jones 205).

Saul was already anointed as king, and “Samuel no longer was judge over Israel, but he was a priest and a prophet. As such, he led the people in a covenant renewal ritual whereby they reaffirmed their allegiance to God, the heavenly king, even though they now had an earthly king” (Longman, Enns and Strauss 111). At this meeting which Prophet Samuel invited all the people to in Gilgal, Samuel’s opinion of the peoples’ problem requiring a spiritual solution more than a political one became apparent to the people. It was here that Samuel invited the people to scrutinize his leadership tenure and come up with an accusation against him. “Before leaving office as a judge, Samuel had to set the record straight and bear witness that his hands were clean and they could find no fault in him” (Wiersbe 511).

The newly installed king was also on seat as the word “His anointed” in verse 3 connotes. It must have been painful for Samuel to conduct this last meeting, which could be regarded as his handing over meeting (Wiersbe, n.pg). Samuel therefore used the occasion to call on the people to attest to the integrity he has built over the years as a judge over Israel. As Delitzsch and Keil remark, this address marks the end of Samuel administration as a judge over Israel. He did not however step aside completely as he in later chapters acted in the capacity of a prophet to represent the people before God, and to maintain the rights of God in relation to the king. In this capacity, he continued to support the king with his advice, until he was compelled to announce his rejection on account of his repeated rebellion against the commands of the Lord, and to anoint David as his successor (Delitzsch and Keil, n.pg).

In this chapter, Samuel’s life of accountability and appropriate use of power was brought to light to which the children of Israel were witness to. In this situation, Samuel was reading having completed his life work, to abdicate that the new leader might take over. He addressed the assembly of the nation at Gilgal with his own defense of his life’s work (Porter 362). He challenged the nation to show that he had been oppressive or unjust; offering to restore what he had robbed them of. The people Paul testified

that he had been righteous. He invoked the witness of God himself and of His anointed and the people agreed (Porter 362).

3.3 Texts of 1 Samuel 12:1-5

3.1.1 Hebrew Text of I Samuel 12:1-5 (BHS; Leningrad Codex B19)

1 וַיֹּאמֶר שְׁמוּאֵל אֶל־כָּל־יִשְׂרָאֵל הִנֵּה שָׁמַעְתִּי בְקִלְכֶם לְכָל אֲשֶׁר־אָמַרְתֶּם לִי וְאַמְלִיךָ עָלֵיכֶם מִלְּךָ:

2 וְעַתָּה הִנֵּה הַמֶּלֶךְ מִתְהַלֵּךְ לִפְנֵיכֶם וְאֲנִי זְקֵנִתִי וְשִׁבְתִּי וּבְנֵי הַנֶּחֱם אִתְּכֶם וְאֲנִי הִתְהַלַּכְתִּי לִפְנֵיכֶם מִנְעֻרֵי עַד־הַיּוֹם הַזֶּה:

3 הֲנִנִּי עֲנוּ בִי נֹגֵד יְהוָה וְנֹגֵד מְשִׁיחוֹ אֶת־שׁוֹר מִי לְקַחְתִּי וְחִמּוֹר מִי לְקַחְתִּי וְאֶת־מִי עָשַׂקְתִּי אֶת־מִירְצוֹתַי וּמִי־דָמִי לְקַחְתִּי כִּפֹּר וְאַעְלִים עֵינַי בּוֹ וְאַשִּׁיב לָכֶם:

4 וַיֹּאמְרוּ לֹא עָשַׂקְתָּנוּ וְלֹא רִצּוֹתָנוּ וְלֹא־לְקַחְתָּ מִי־אִישׁ מֵאֻמָּה:

5 וַיֹּאמֶר אֲלֵיהֶם עַד יְהוָה בְּכֶם וְעַד מְשִׁיחוֹ הַיּוֹם הַזֶּה כִּי לֹא מָצָאתֶם בְּיָדִי מֵאֻמָּה וַיֹּאמְרוּ עַד:

3.1.2 Researcher's Working Translation of 1 Samuel 12:1-5

1. Samuel said to all Israel, "I have listened to everything you said to me and have set a king over you. 2. Now you have a king as your leader. As for me, I am old and gray, and my sons are here with you. I have been your leader from my youth until this day. 3. Here I stand. Testify against me in the presence of the Lord and his anointed. Whose ox have I taken? Whose donkey have I taken? Whom have I cheated? Whom have I oppressed? From whose hand have I accepted a bribe to make me shut my eyes? If I have done any of these, I will make it right." 4. "You have not cheated or oppressed us," they replied. "You have not taken anything from anyone's hand." 5. Samuel said to them, "The Lord is witness against you, and also his anointed is witness this day, that you have not found anything in my hand." "He is witness," they said.

3.4 Delineation of 1 Samuel 12:1-5

The researcher delineated the pericope of 1 Samuel 12:1-5 because the five verses talk about prophet Samuel's fulfillment of the bid of the people by giving them a king; in the transition period he testified to his uncompromising character while in office as their leader and to that the people concurred to. Within these five verses, Samuel declares his doing the bidding of the people of Israel, then he moves to

testify about his good leadership and even invites the people to evaluate his leadership and finally they clear him of bad leadership, making God a witness to their testimony.

3.5 Exegesis of 1 Samuel 12:1-5

After the victory of Saul over the Ammonites in I Samuel 11, the nation began to look for a king for leadership. Here, Samuel is helping Israel to make the transition from his leadership to Saul's leadership (theocracy to monarchy). Samuel makes this clear when he says, "*Now you have a king as your leader. As for me, I am old and gray.*" Samuel is telling Israel that his day is over, and Saul's day is beginning (Guzik, n.pg). Here, Samuel gives the people of Israel an account of the last revolution and of the present posture of their government.

In verse one, the first thing that is interesting about prophet Samuel is that he was a listening leader. Samuel made a declaration to all Israel, "I have listened to everything you said to me and have set a king over you." The Hebrew word (שמעתי) translated "I have listened" is from the verb, *shama*. It implies 'to hear intelligently often with implication of attention, and obedience' (Strong, n.8085, 119). It carries the idea of hearing and acting appropriately with due diligence. Prophet Samuel, after hearing the request of the people, acted on it appropriately and selflessly. From Samuel's declaration, he noted it clearly known that it was not his idea to appoint a king over Israel. This idea began in the hearts of Israel, not in the heart and mind of God. God allowed it and directed its execution, but it was the voice of the people that prompted it (Guzik, n.pg). He was old, and therefore the more able to advise them. Though he was personally hurt by their desire for a king and disagreed with it as a policy, he did not simply dismiss it. He took it to God, and then agreed to do what the people wanted.

For Samuel, he had spent his days in their office; he began betimes to be among them and had continued long, so he declared to them, "As for me, I am old and gray, and my sons are here with you. I have been your leader from my youth until this day." Prophet Samuel in verse two reminds them that he was already old and grey-headed, and his sons are with them. He also points out that he has been their leader since his youth. Samuel pointed that the people are fully aware of how he has conducted his life affairs since he was a youth. He had been a long, steady and immaculate servant of the public (Clark, n.pg). No aspect of his life is shrouded in secrecy; and if there has been any form of abuse of power in his living, the people would have known. His life has been lived before them and they should be able to judge whether he led them in integrity or not.

Samuel also presented his sons before the people for them to call his sons to an account for anything they have done amiss. Samuel presented them so that if they are proven guilty of any wrong, they will be prosecuted by a due course of law, punish them and oblige them to make restitution. Nothing is said of their earlier complaint about his two sons in 8:1-5; but the reference to his sons here in v. 2 may imply that he had dismissed them from their posts in Beersheba and brought them back home (Payne 308).

On the part of his children, Samuel might have pardoned his own sons, who have acted improperly before he quitted the government; but though he was the most tender of parents, he would not, but abandoned them to national justice, with only a tacit solicitation of mercy: Behold, my sons are with you! They have acted improperly; I deprived them of their authority; they are amenable to you for their past conduct; I have walked uprightly and disinterestedly among you; they have not followed my steps: but can you forgive them for their father's sake? (Clarke, n.pg). Also, Barnes says that these words of Samuel intimate that he had deprived them of public employ, and reduced them to a level with the common people (n.pg).

In verse 3 of the text, Samuel is seen clearing himself from all suspicion or imputation of mismanagement, while the administration was in his hand. He solemnly appeals to them concerning his good leadership while in office. Samuel challenges the people: "Here I stand. Testify against me in the presence of the Lord and his anointed. Whose ox have I taken? Whose donkey have I taken? Whom have I cheated? Whom have I oppressed? From whose hand have I accepted a bribe to make me shut my eyes? If I have done any of these, I will make it right." (1 Samuel 12:3 NIV)." The Hebrew word (עָנָה) translated "testify" is the word "*anu*" and it is from "*anah*" which is an invitation to shout, announce, cry out to make public or specifically to testify (Strong, n.6030, 90). He presents himself for public testimony about his long years of leadership in the nation. In today's parlance, he let go of his immunity and asked that he should be publicly accused of any act of oppression, corruption, bribery and perversion of justice to suit himself or his family (Ellicott 544).

The New King James Version uses "... witness against me..." The word "*witness*" has dual usage in the Scripture. It may refer to one who tells what he has seen or personally experienced in a court of law. The term may also refer to the testimony which he has given (Elwell 2154). The second meaning is implied in this passage. In the judicial procedure outlined in the Old Testament, one witness was not

adequate for personal testimony against anyone, but two or three witnesses were required. This principle was ingrained into the Jewish law and reiterated as in the New Testament (Elwell 2155).

Furthermore, Samuel asks “*From whose hand have I accepted a bribe to make me shut my eyes?*” The Hebrew word (כֶּפֶר) translated as bribe is the word “*kopher*” which has its root from the verb meaning “to hide, conceal, or cover up” (Omason and Ellington, n.pg). And in Strong’s, the word means to bribe, ransom (n.3724, 57). Hence, it literally signifies a covering, and was used of money given by a guilty person to induce the judge to close or “blind his eyes”. Furthermore, the Hebrew expression “to blind my eyes” means “to cause me to look away from the wrong that the person has done. Figuratively then, this kind of a bribe was understood to be a redemption price, that is a ransom. It therefore means that given to buy off a guilty person. Such persons are generally powerful men who have oppressed and wronged others (Spence-Jones 206). As Warren comments, in the East, it was common that civil officials would use their offices to make money. Samuel however did not follow that route. He obeyed the Law of Moses and kept his hands clean (Wiersbe, n.pg).

By asking this question, Samuel intended to first convince them of the injury they have done him in setting him aside even when they had nothing amiss to charge him of. Samuel preserved his own reputation. There is emphasis on the fact that Samuel had *taken* nothing unjustly from anyone. This description of Samuel makes a strong contrast with his own description of Kings in 8:11 – 18, which shows them taking one thing after another from their subjects (Payne 308).

It is possible that those that heard of Samuel’s being rejected as he was would be ready to suspect that certainly he had done some evil thing, or he would never have been ill-treated. He was opening his life up for everyone to scrutinize. Samuel knew that it is God's measurement of our lives and ministries that counts most, but listening to the way the people see him will make him more free among them. Samuel, designed to leave a good name behind him, so he designed to leave his successor a good example before him so that the successor can write after his copy and write fair. He begins with a vindication of himself for he that will, with confidence, tell area of wrong so that he too can see to it that he himself be clear.

According to Walton et al, “It is common for a ruler to blame the country's problems on a previous administration. It was also not uncommon in the ancient world for charges to be trumped up against anyone who might be seen as a threat to the power of the ruler currently in power. It was therefore

understandable that Samuel would want to take steps to procure an affirmation of his innocence in matters of government” (297-298). He needed to verify that he had not been accused of any injustice.

The words of Adams Clarke are very vital to this action of Prophet Samuel. He says,

... He had accumulated no riches for himself; he had procured none for his friends; nor had one needy dependent been provided for out of the public purse. He might have pardoned his sons, who had acted improperly before he quitted the government; but though he was the most tender of parents, he would not, but abandoned them to national justice, with only a tacit solicitation of mercy: Behold, my sons are with you! They have acted improperly; I deprived them of their authority; they are amenable to you for their past conduct; I have walked uprightly and disinterestedly among you; they have not followed my steps: but can you forgive them for their father's sake? As a minister of justice, he abandons them to their fate; as a tender father, he indirectly and modestly pleads for them on the ground of his services. Had he not acted thus in both these relations, he would have been unworthy of that character which he so deservedly bears” (n.pg).

Woolfe said of Samuel, “Samuel did not passively respond or react to an investigation of his possessions. He initiated it himself. He invited investigation of his honesty and integrity, down to the last ox and donkey, promising to return anything that might have been immorally appropriated, no matter how insignificant. And he promised to rectify the least evidence of impropriety or dishonest gain” (7).

Samuel in this appeal acquits himself from, firstly, that he had never, under any protest whatsoever, taking back which was not his own, ox or ass, he had never detained their cattle for tribute, fines or forfeitures, now used their service without paying for it. Secondly, he had never before did roughly with those he dealt, nor oppressed those that were under his power. Also, he have never taken bribes to pervert justice, nor was ever biased by favour for affection to give judgment in a cause against his conscience. He calls upon those that were hurt to bear witness concerning his conduct, for he says, “*Here I stand. Testify against me....*” (NIV).

In response to Samuel’s speech the people answer thus “*You have not cheated or oppressed us,*” they replied, “*You have not taken anything from anyone's hand*” (1 Sam 12:4). Upon his appeal, Samuel is honorably acquitted. The people assert that Samuel has not forcefully taken anything from them.

Neither has he coerced them into giving him anything, nor oppressed them or deprived them of what they should have benefitted from his leadership. He did not expect that they will do him honour at parting, though he well deserved it, and therefore mentioned not any of the good services he had done them, for which they ought to have applauded him and returned him the thanks of the house; all he desired was that they should do him justice, and that they did.

The people readily owning stated that he had not made his term of oppressive to them nor used his power to their wrong; he have not made it expensive to them; for they said, “...*you have not defrauded us or oppressed us or taken anything from the hand of anyone.*”(NRSV). This means that he have not only been righteous, but generous. He have not defrauded anyone. He had not oppressed anyone or denied anyone a fair hearing of his or her case (Klein 84). The people's response to Samuel's challenge is testimony to a life of dignity and transparent lifestyle.

Samuel's reply to the people is significant. “*The Lord is witness against you, and also his anointed is witness this day, that you have not found anything in my hand;*” (v. 5). And the people replied that the LORD is witness. Samuel set the seal on his accountability by calling on the Lord and Saul to be his witnesses. Samuel knew that people might be afraid to speak up but God knows what no one else may know. God is the righteous judge and the one who will make the final judgment on the integrity with which Samuel has worked. Samuel was acting as a role model for Saul – a young man just coming into leadership. He was setting the standard that all should maintain. This honorable testimony borne to Samuel's integrity is left upon record to his honour. “The Lord is witness, ‘*who searcheth the heart and his anointed is witness, who trieth overt acts;* and the people agrees to it: He is witness.” Israel knew Samuel had been a good, godly leader. He had not led them for what he can get from them, but what he could give to them (Guzik, n.pg). This testimony of the people made him free from all charges before them.

3.6 Theological Conclusions

1. Abuse of power is not expected of in Christian leadership.
2. It is not enough to lead but the most important is how the leader led the people who will someday give testimony of the leadership.
3. Listening and responding properly to those being led in any context is the first step to achieving good leadership without abuse of power in any Christian leadership position.

4. The place God occupies in a leader's heart and life is important in determining his/her leadership status. This would have prompted him/her to present himself/herself for public scrutiny.
5. Christian leaders need to see themselves as Gods' representatives before their followers.
6. Like Samuel, Christian leaders should account for their administrations. They are to honestly give the accounts of their times in office.
7. Christian leaders are supposed never to under any situation collect bribe, nor oppress, nor deal roughly with the people they are leading.
8. Christian leaders who did well in office have the opportunity of being cleared of any form of abuse by the people.
9. The peoples' verdict is a testimony that a Christian leader can serve without abusing his/her power.
10. God, other leaders and the people are witnesses to the actions of Christian leaders.
11. The thought that God is the principal witness is something that should make any Christian leader, especially Church leaders at whatever level to serve with fear of God and integrity.

The exegetical study has examined the leadership of Samuel. The passage reveals that Samuel never abused his power. He did not use his privileged position to cheat, oppress or defraud people. He refrained from taking bribe to cover or look away from the crime of an individual. Having observed his life from childhood, no one had any charge against him of cheat, oppression or bribery. Hence, the people in one accord answered, "You have not cheated...." This is a clear demonstration of appropriate use of power in leadership. It further connotes that in the sight of all Israel, Samuel's life and ministry was characterized with integrity of heart. Samuel not only cleared his own character, but set an example before Saul.

Noteworthy is the fact that Samuel's proper exercise of power while in office stemmed from his intrinsic belief in God and adherence to the teachings of the scriptures. It is evident that if Christian leaders have true reverence for God and hold on to biblical injunctions, they can serve with integrity in any leadership position, especially in the Church. This is irrespective of their frailty as humans.

CHAPTER FOUR

CHRISTIAN LEADERSHIP IN IHECHIOWA AND ABUSE OF POWER

This chapter handles abuse of power in Christian leadership in Ihechiowa. It began by giving a brief history of Ihechiowa. It investigates abuse of power in Christian leadership in Ihechiowa, causes of abuse of power among Christian leaders in Ihechiowa, effects of abuse of power among Christian leaders in Ihechiowa. From Samuel's use of power in his leadership as testified to in 1 Samuel 12:1-5, lessons are drawn for Christian leaders in Ihechiowa. The researcher here also proffers strategies for preventing abuse of power among Christian leaders in Ihechiowa.

4.1 Brief History of Ihechiowa

Ihechiowa people are Igbo of the south eastern extract of Nigeria, found among the people of old Bende division presently in Arochukwu Local Government Area of Abia State. They speak their native Igbo tongue called Ihe. The community is bounded by Ohafia on the north, Ututu and Arochukwu on the south, Abam on the west and Ukwu Ibom and Biakpan of Cross River State on the north east. Ihechiowa is the second largest clan in Arochukwu local government, after Abam. Ihechiowa was divided into two major sections, Ikwun and Eleoha before the creation of the autonomous communities (Ogbuanu ix).

The clan lies within longitudes 7° , 4° , and 8° East, and latitude 5° , 3° North. A conspicuous physical feature here is the range which extends from Udi in Enugu State through Okigwe, Ohafia, Ihechiowa, and Ututu, up to the Oban Hill in Cross River State and thence to the Cameroun mountains. This ridge runs across Ihechiowa territory from north to south, and divides the clan into two. But it makes no difference because the people are historically and culturally homogenous. Two rivers form the natural boundaries of Ihechiowa. One is the Uduma which forms the northwestern boundary of Ihechiowa and Abam. The other is the Iyi Ocha which separates Ihechiowa from Arochukwu in the southwest.

Ihechiowa has seventeen (17) villages of Abuoru, Achara, Amaetiti, Amafia, Amamiri, Agbor, Atan, Ebemofia, Ndi Okpo, Nkporo, Obichie, Obinto, Umuye, Umuzomgbo, Uburu, Okpo, and Umuchiakuma. Ikwun is made up of Abuoru, Agbor, Atan, Ebem ofia, Ndiokpo, Nkporo, Obichie, Obinto, Umuye, Umuzomgbo, and Uburu, while Eleoha is made up of Achara, Amaetiti, Amafia, Amamiri, Okpo, and Umuchiakuma. There are eight (8) autonomous communities – Ogige Ihe, Ata

Igboukwu, Ikwun, Eleoha, Isi Eleoha, Odum Chiakuma, Okpurukpu Enyi and Ukanyi Edegiri (Ogbuanu ix).

The formation of Ihechiowa by the patriarchs was acts of their bravery as warriors who were heroes and hunters. Those patriarchs the sons of Chiowa and their descendants were brave men indeed. They were- Okwun, Diogu Ukwu (aka Ele), Ogorioka, Mgbonweza, Abaga Itam, Itam Ada, Oburu Oku, Ekuma Ukwu, Chiemkuma, Obi Ekuma, Ogori Mgbo, Ebele Okike, Owara Eke, Nkorie Nkwoma Uko, Iyioma Nja, Amami and Okpo Nja. They were the founders of the various Ihechiowa villages. The patriarch Chiowa meaning (God of the earth) founded a community of unique people endowed by God with strength relative to their geographical location. The patriarchs of Ihechiowa migrated from Agbor Ibeku in Umuahia North Local Government Area of Abia State. It was told that there were mysterious occurrences that took place which resulted to famine, diseases and deaths in a small hamlet called Ihe. It was repercussion for their various evils and other abominable acts committed by the people (Ogbuanu 1).

People oppressed one another: strong men oppressed the weak. They forcefully took their property, wives as well as children from the powerless and turned them to slaves. It was a time of survival of the fittest as men could kill others unjustly. Some slept and did not wake up while some got missing without traces. People lived in fear of what could happen to them next. The situation was tagged "Agha-Ogbutu and Agha Nkpuru." They all resulted to famine, diseases and strange deaths. Crops were no longer yielding for them. The people consulted an oracle and they were told that it was nemesis for their evil and that there was no end to it rather that the end was total extinction of everyone by death. So in order not to die the patriarchs Chiowa, Ekuma, Ekukinam, Ebemoku and others with their families decided to leave Ibeku for another settlement. The year of the departure was not told (Ogbuanu 1-2).

They left and journeyed to a place called Orie-ofia where they settled. In Orie-ofia, they met the inhabitants of the land, the Uzuakoli people who fought them but could not prevail against them. though they stayed for many years in Orie-ofia but their problem continued that they had to go back to the oracle for another consultation. The answer was still the same. The next decision was moving again from Orie-ofia to another place where they could settle and live in peace without fear. So they left Uzuakoli. At Uzuakoli, Ekukinan and Ebemeoku with their families decided to move to a different direction while Ekuma who had become the leader due to the death of Chiowa in Orie-Ofia took

another direction. Uzuakoli people were happy for the development and quickly they took their land and other things they left behind. It was during that journey to another settlement that they suffered so much loss of their children and wives. They decided to seek for alternative way to solve their problem than consulting oracle (Ogbuanu 2).

The search for a permanent home was the dream of everyone as they moved through land and forests, under rain and sun eating anything they could lay their hands on. They journeyed to a place called Ihenta and the nemesis also followed them to Ihenta. The situation became so terrible that grave diggers became popular among them. The situation helped in remolding their life as it became a serious nightmare (Ogbuanu 2). The story was that before their arrival to Ihenta a man of Ihenta had a dream of unknown visitors to Ihenta. Their ancestors had told them to always accommodate strangers that came their way. So when they received the news of a crowd of visitors they rejoiced, when they remembered what their ancestors told them about the gains of receiving strangers. The chief priest of Ihenta prayed a prayer calling the gods of Ihenta to turn to their visitors to add to them the goodness of the land and to take care of the people including Ihenta people. It was the people of Ihenta that made it possible for Ihechiowa people to realize their dream of good life (Ogbuanu 3).

The exit of the people of Ihe from Orie-ofia in their request for a permanent place affected the people of Uzuakli, as the help they were rendering to them in the cultivation of their farm lands ceased. The far distant journey to the next place really tested their strength which seemed almost impossible. However, after several days' journey they landed on a new farm land owned by the people of Ihenta. When the farmers saw them, they ran to inform the villagers of the unusual crowd they saw. The migrants stopped at the entrance of the village while they came out to meet them and also to know their mission. They introduced themselves as the people of Ihe while the host village introduced themselves as the people of Ihenta. After narrating their ordeal, they were welcomed by Ihenta. Food and drinks were arranged for them by Nna Mba Alugulugu who was the founder of Ihenta along with two other leaders of Ihenta, Nna Eme Ekeh and Nna Uka Ekeh. Ihenta people showed much hospitality to Ihechiowa people as they considered them to be their brothers probably because of the resemblance in their names (Ogbuanu 3). The people were not in a hurry to leave Ihenta, due to the kindness shown to them that they decided to stay with Ihenta people. Thereafter, an area of land was shown to them where they stayed and built houses of their own (Ogbuanu 3-4).

Ihechiowa people appreciated the hospitality and kindness of Ihenta and all the other provisions made available for them. But they wanted a place where no one had occupied, where they could live and build a permanent home for themselves, so that their generations unborn would not struggle with other people. They wanted to establish a new community and a simple society void of the atrocities, abominations and nemesis they experienced at Ibeku. Then Ekuma after much deliberation with others expressed their intention to leave to Nna Mba Alugulugu, Nna Eme Ekeh, Nna Uka Ekeh and other elders of Ihenta. They appreciated them for the assistance given to them and also promised to maintain the cordial relationship that existed between them. In turn the people of Ihenta expressed their displeasure over their departure (Ogbuanu 4-5).

Finally, a day was fixed for the departure and it was a big ceremony for both villages. The Ihenta hunters were armed for the journey to escort them to a certain point into the forest. It was more difficult for the people as they went through the forest. The Ihenta hunters had left them at the middle of the journey. A surprised incident occurred after their departure, the dogs barked for days continuously without a break. The dogs had made friends with the people so they were not happy with the situation. An oracle was consulted and the solution was that the hunters must go to the bush, to hunt for the dogs in place of the good food they were receiving from the Ihechiowa people, which when they did the dogs stopped barking (Ogbuanu 5).

On their departure from Ihenta, they moved onward towards the south, until they arrived Ogige Ihe, their desired destination. An area inhabited by no man, the land of their choice which is the present day location of Ihechiowa. When they arrived, the area was a vast forest but the humid nature of the area suggested to them the kind of simple and quiet society they had in mind. Also availability of water and other natural provisions were put into consideration, for the area looked more like already made home for them which attracted the name “Ogige Ihe.” They began their new life by erecting shelters for themselves (Ogbuanu 5).

4.2 Manifestations of Abuse of Power in Christian Leadership in Ihechiowa

In Ihechiowa, abuse of power among church leaders is not only on non-verbal actions but include other areas, as it is in line with Nunez and Gonzalez’s definition in chapter two (2.5), that abuse of power is: “Any abusive behaviour that is expressed in non-verbal cues, words, behaviour, or attitudes which are systematically repeated, destroying the mental dignity of a person, and thus, jeopardizing employment or degrading the organizational climate” (36). Those interviewed from the context of this study

responded in varying words to what they think that abuse of power is in Christian leadership as manifested in Ihechiowa by Church leaders. The following areas were pointed by the respondents:

i. Spiritual Pride

Okali said that the abuse of power among church leaders in Ihechiowa occurs more in spiritual pride. He noted that their pastor spiritualizes his actions by claiming the Church is doing God's work and he has insights and direct communication from God. he tells them to contribute sometimes as a result of a revelation God told him. That the church will get blessed by that contribution and those money goes into his personal purse. He will use comments that make people feel guilty in order to persuade them to follow whatsoever he wants or desires from the members (*Oral Interview*). This attitude truly has crippled not just ministers in the field but also those on the making. According to Baxter, "...one of our most heinous and palpable sins is pride. This is a sin that hath too much interest in the best of us, but which is more hateful and inexcusable in us than in other men. Yet is it so prevalent in some of us, that it indicts our discourses, it chooses our company, it form our countenances, it put the accent and emphasis upon our words (137). Uchenna said that he believes that it is spiritual pride that led his church leader to fall off the track of his calling. When a minister thinks he has already attempted a level in life, the tendency is for him to depend on his strength and firm and then forget God who has lifted him up. An illustration to this is the case of a church leader who was transferred to another church within Ihechiowa, he refused the transfer because of pride and opened his own church stealing members from his former church; he claimed that he had all it takes to be fulfilled in ministry: cars, spiritual gifts and others (*Oral Interview*). But this is in contrast to the life of Samuel. He was rather a man of humility. His administration was characterized by a servant-leadership. In it, he was not high-handed on the people.

ii. Playing to be God

According to Francis, abuse of power manifests in Ihechiowa among church leaders when they begin to play God. One of the ways power abuse is carried out is when church leaders play God before their followers (*Oral Interview*). This is "power posturing" In the words of Johnson and VanVonderen (63). Church leaders often flaunt their personal opinions and impressions, so that they become equal with God's. Statements such as "God said this to me", or "God has revealed this to me", can be so innocent, yet misleading. Bongbong refers to this danger, when he asserts: "It (i.e., church leadership) presumes everything it does is good and acceptable. Furthermore, it is hard for the church to critically analyze

religious programmes; since everything is done for God, and is presumed, unquestionably, to be suitable and acceptable” (19). The researcher has in person observed how a church leader in Ihechiowa intimated that God had spoken to him about his member contesting the local government elections. God even hinted that he was going to win. Strangely, another church leader in the same village, lobbying for his member as well, who was contesting the same seat, was also explicitly telling the constituents that God has revealed to him that his relation must run for the elections. Sadly, both lost the election at the end. The question is: Was God conveying two sets of contradictory messages to these church leaders at the same time?

iii. Exercise of Authority in the Church by Coercion

In Ihechiowa, power abuse in Christian or church leadership also involves an inappropriate use of authority in the church by coercion. Some of the church leaders use force to achieve their aim. They place some of their church members on duress (Amah, *Oral Interview*). The pastor from Ascension Church that impregnated his two female members was reported by the two girls to have told them that because he is a man of God, the act is not a sin. And that the scripture said that the men of God should be respected. Scripture can often be used to bolster this. Since most people in Churches are marginally literate, it is relatively easy for this to occur. This proves that scriptural authority which provides church leaders with the basis for effecting power action in the church, can unfortunately result to actions can easily go beyond what is approved by scripture. Illustratively, it is quite easy for church leaders to use their position to impose certain lifestyle values on their members in the church; standards not explicitly stated in scripture. Again, in one of the churches, a young church leader was fond of using the pulpit to advocate preference for a particular dress code. He described for the members the dress pattern that is equated with holiness. Actually, in some cases, this issue has been pushed to the extreme, so that church members have broken up as a result.

iv. Suppression of Members

Other respondents added that suppressions are also seen among some Church leaders in Ihechiowa; and this constitutes abuse of power. Okwuagwu said that most ordinary believers in some churches do not know their particular gift, which is why their gift is underused. Perhaps this may be due to simple ignorance. But, in most cases, the laity is simply suppressed by the church leader (*Oral Interview*). Referring to how church organization contributes to perpetrating this unhealthy state, Bongbong remarks, “A pyramid-type structure that has one person at the top consequently promotes colonialism,

and a paternalistic spirit” (19). In Assemblies of God Church, the Bible Study teacher never permitted the members of the church to ask questions after his teaching. He will rather tell them that they do not need to ask questions, they are expected to sit quietly through the study, Sunday after Sunday. Often, the only meaningful contribution they are expected to offer is from their pockets or purses which they call “Sunday School Offering”. Teachings on tithing and giving are expansive in some of the churches. In Ihechiowa, a mixture of emphases, related to giving, has brought about a great deal of confusion (John, *Oral Interview*). Truly participating, as members of the body of Christ, is simply not an option. This can be excused where believers are fairly-recent converts. But, in most cases, believers, who have been converts for decades, are still unable to contribute meaningfully to the work of the gospel, as maturing disciples of Jesus Christ.

v. Withholding Knowledge from Members

Njoku pointed the problem of church leaders withholding knowledge from their members. Consequently, many believers possess a shallow understanding of God’s word, even after years of ministry. This is most evident when the members of the church show a careless attitude towards what they profess in their daily lives. He also sadly noted that, the teachings of scripture are presented as mostly matters of the mind, application is complicated, and, therefore, unable to transform life (*Oral Interview*). Such situations resemble the use of scripture by the Pharisees and Sadducees, to prevent ordinary believers from accessing their leadership domain, or questioning their authority. In opposition, Jesus pithily remarked: “It is enough for the student to be like his teacher, and the servant like his master” (Tippett 302). If a significant number of ordinary believers are still biblically illiterate, after years of ministry, what is the problem? Is this a deliberate scheme to keep members dependent on the church leaders? Certainly, it could be.

The researcher observed that there had been some ministers who never completed their period of years in their posted churches because they abused their power. If it is not the news of them always threatening the members, it will be of subjecting them to laws that are not proper. Closely connected to the abuses of power is the mistreatment of subordinates. While the mistreatment of subordinates is an example of the Church leader overstepping his/her authority, it is also a direct consequence of that type of abuse of power. Some church leaders in Ihechiowa have been observed to have insufficient respect for their members in the church and the ways they treat them are improper. It means that these church leaders make use of coercive methods, such as brute force, inappropriate persuasion, and threats. Also,

some of them think of themselves so highly than the members of their church; this is pride in action. It is not a gainsaying that it is noticed that in spite of the biblical teaching of the priesthood of all believers in many of the churches, some church leaders and their members have an no good clergy-laity relationship. As one of the respondents lamented, “This has created a discrepancy between the ideal teaching of the priesthood of all believers and the practice of the church leaders” (Kalu, *Oral Interview*).

vi. Manifestation of Unethical Character by Church Leaders

Another respondent, Sunday Kalu narrated how the minister in their church was removed after a year of his stay in posted parish because of unethical character. He said that this church leader will always abuse the members, even while preaching on the pulpit; call them poor people who could not afford his monthly salary and sometimes, threaten to slap some women if he hears any noise from their seat while he is preaching (Oral Interview 10/9/2022). Benjamin Uche, an elder of one of the churches, supported this in a story he told about a minister in their church in Ihechiowa who will reject some food items from the women in the church because he thinks that the cooking items is not complete. On another occasion, he told the deacons of the church that he would not preach on Sunday except they buy recharge card for him – and he meant it. This same church leader also maltreats any seminarian sent to him for ministerial supervision; this he do to the extent that any gift given to this seminarian by a church member he will collect it from him (Oral Interview 21/9/2022). This attitude of misuse of power was not seen in the life of Samuel. He did not use his office to oppress people, neither did he use it to make troubles, rather he led the people in the fear of God.

vii. Financial Misappropriation

Financial misappropriation is another area where church leaders manifest their abuse of power in Ihechiowa. This is the act of misusing the finances of the church. Several church leaders have entered into this trap. According to Bwosh, financial misappropriation is affecting the church and is rampart in the church more than sexual misconduct (n.pg). If one is unable to manage finances of the church, it therefore mean that such a church leader will not also manage the church well and the probability is that, people will not also support well in giving because financial integrity is lost. One of the areas in which some church leaders in Ihechiowa can and have experienced immense damage to their integrity and credibility is in the area of church finances. Knapp said that, “Research suggests that ethical issues related to money are much more common problems for church leaders than sexual misconduct and

other issues that have grabbed headlines of late.” He continued, “Indeed, ethical issues involving money are a growing problem in the church, undermining congregational life and effective church leadership ministry. It is likely that financial disputes cause more churches to split than theological disputes” (n.pg).

In the interview carried out by the researcher, one of the respondents, Ekem, frankly asked, “What in the world possesses a church leader, an ordained man of God, to use church finances – the tithes and offerings of congregants – for personal use? And then make the matter of financial abuse even worse by not being forthcoming by acknowledging the misdeed and immediately re-paying his church?” and “What might possess a church leader to distort truth by claiming he didn’t know he wasn’t supposed to spend church funds for personal needs and that he had been allowed at his previous churches to do so?” (*Oral Interview*). However, another respondent, Njasi rather sympathetically said that she do not blame some of these church leaders who divert church funds into their private account because some of our churches fail to take good care of them. As she narrated, she said that she has seen a church where the church leader have to write a letter to the finance board before any amount of money could be released to him. She showed her disapproval of such rule since it could make some church leaders to begin to tamper with the church money (*Oral interview*). The researcher agreed with what Njasi said because he had seen a situation where a church leader forged purchase receipts in order to increase the money for the church when paying him. When he went to buy a refrigerator for the church, he told the seller to increase the actual amount by ten percent (10%). When he was asked, his reply was that since the church has refused to take care of him, he will devise means of getting that money they do not want to willingly give. Such situations are disheartening and need to be attended to by the church.

Another form of financial mismanagement in the church among some church leaders in Ihechiowa is using a particular offering or donation for what it was not meant for. A church leader picked offence when a woman in his church asked him thus, “Sir, for about three years you have church leadered us and we have been giving offerings for the poor in the poor-people box but I have never heard of one helped with it, why? The question of the woman was true from her observation but the church leader has always used the offerings to do some other thing. A respondent said that people in the church may be tempted to stop giving a particular offering or donation when it is glaring that the purpose of its giving is not what it is used for (Nnukwu, *Oral Interview*). In these churches, most Sundays the church leader pressures people to give more. In contrast, Samuel’s life and leadership was devoid of financial

misappropriation. For as he declared, as well as the testimony of the people, he was free of bribery or extortion. He never meddled with the things that belonged to the people throughout his tenure in office.

viii. Prosperity Gospel Preaching

Prosperity gospel is another menace seen among some church leaders in some churches in Ihechiowa; they have joined some erroneous Pentecostal preachers to preach wrongly about giving and wealth. Prosperity gospel (sometimes referred to as the prosperity theology, the health and wealth gospel, the gospel of success, or seed faith) is a religious belief among some Christians that financial blessing and physical well-being are always the will of God for them, and that faith, positive speech, and donations to religious reasons will increase one's material wealth (Bitrus 42). Prosperity theology views the Bible as a contract between God and humans: if humans have faith in God, God must surely deliver security and prosperity (Harrison 76). According to Ugochukwu, Church leaders in Ihechiowa who preach this gospel maintain that God wants people to be prosperous, especially financially as far as the rule of constant giving to the man of God is maintained (*Oral Interview*). Adherents to the Prosperity Gospel believe that wealth is a sign of God's blessing and is compensation for prayer and for giving beyond the minimum tithe to one's church, or other religious causes.

Uzodinma noted that the logical extension of the Prosperity Gospel—sometimes explicit, sometimes not, depending on the preacher—is that the poor are poor because of a lack of faith, that is, that poverty is the fault of the poor themselves. As such, they argue that they should model their lives after Jesus' by living lavishly, in stark contrast to orthodox interpretations of the Gospels. In this sense, adherents believe God to be very interested in their financial status. An Evangel Church pastor had once preached that poverty, far from being a blessing, is a sign of God's disfavor; thus, Christians have a duty to deal only with the apparent lack of faith among the poor and not their poverty itself (*Oral Interview*). Some of the church leaders in these churches in Ihechiowa have started embracing and teaching prosperity gospel to the members of their churches. They maintain that if one does not give to the service of God, then the blessings of God are not for such person and poverty is a sign of being separated from God; a believer cannot be poor.

Another respondent confirmed this practice among church leaders in Ihechiowa by narrating how a church leader in one of the Pentecostal churches in Ihechiowa tells his members to come and drop money in order to claim a blessing; sometimes it will be to touch his shoes with the money in order for them to be rich or have financial breakthrough in their businesses (Nnukwu, *Oral Interview*). Another

respondent, lamented how a church leader used the idea of “Sowing at the Apostle’s feet” (which is prevalent among the preachers of this gospel) to deceive her into borrowing more than thirty thousand naira (30,000) in order to tap into his anointing so that his business will flourish and prosper, even when he had no money in his account. She also narrated how she was disappointed being a member of her church because their new church leader preached that anyone who is poor is faithless and is not a child of God (because God never promised his children suffering). She out cried that she no longer feel as a true child of God because she feels she cannot fit into God’s plan (Imo, *Oral Interview*).

ix. Manipulation of Prophecy

False prophecy is another way church leaders in Ihechiowa abuse their power. According to Onyenachi, it is no longer news that in some churches in Ihechiowa today, false prophecy prevails and the vulnerable or average Christians falls into the trap of the ,church leaders who indulge in manipulating prophecies (*Oral Interview*). Especially, Ihechiowa being a rural area where people are not very much enlightened, these church leaders enjoy extorting money from them and as well bringing problems into various families as a result of what he or she prophesied.

Another respondent, said that this menace of false prophecies prospers because many persons and families are more interested in prophecies, in church leaders that give prophecies and in churches that are prophetic in nature – so to say. People like these no longer consider if the foundation of the church is built on the Word of God or if the prophecies are from God. The respondent also cited examples of some homes, marriages, relationships that are now broken because of a prophecy given by a false prophet that parades himself as a true man of God. He also lamented the fact that many church leaders in his home parish who were known to be true men of God have started diluting the Word of God which they preach. Others have started getting charms that will help them give prophecies to his church members so that they will not leave to other churches in search of prophecies. These, he described to be outlandish and unbiblical (Joseph, *Oral Interview*).

x. Selfish Ambition

Another respondent identified that a church leader is said to have abused power when the leader uses his/her position for personal gain or selfish ambition. This can result in physical and emotional harm, and is associated with the leader demanding subservience and praise, and can be caused by having a need to be popular (Nneoke Oti, Oral interview 5/10/2022). This response is in line with the possible

temptations of the abuser of power seen in chapter two (2.3), where the leader wants by all means to be relevant, spectacular and powerful. Furthermore, it became obvious that if leaders are not prepared to have their ideas challenged, are authoritarian and do not listen to others, they are considered to be abusive.

Some of the respondents gave other personal testimonies of abuse of power by church leaders in Ihechiowa, especially their own church leaders. The following are some of the testimonies: Njoku from Apostolic Church said, “The pastor made us to follow him without question and did not accept critique, taking matters personally. He manipulated us through words and actions (portrayed us as being unable, untrustworthy, ungodly)” (*Oral interview*). Uchenna from Assemblies of God Church lamented, “Our youth church leader’s wife spreads confidential information gained at board meeting, resulting in strife and lies” (*Oral Interview*). Okike from Ascension Church said, “Our church split as a result of a group of people in the church who promoted their herbal healing product, forcing them to buy it, whereas they asked for prayer for healing in church. They would be contacted after church for a sales pitch with the excuse that it was kind to want to sell the product to people who could be healed through using it. The evangelist and the prophet posted to our Church and their wives instigated the situation” (*Oral Interview*).

Okali from Presbyterian Church of Nigeria lamented, “A Revd. minister sent to our parish sometimes rejected the food stuffs given to him by the parish women, saying that it is below his standard in ministry; In another occasion, Parish minister and board member manipulated a project that almost caused division in the church” (*Oral Interview*). Oti from Evangel Church said, “One of our deacons controlled decision-making in our Church. He spread rumours about anyone who disagreed with him. He also misused finances for his own purpose and thought he was entitled to it, since he was the senior deacon” (*Oral Interview*).

4.3 Causes of Abuse of Power among Christian Leaders in Ihechiowa

The factors that have contributed to abuse of power among church Christian leaders in Ihechiowa are as follows:

i. Insecurity

Insecurity was found by the researcher as a factor that can cause church leaders in Ihechiowa to abuse their power. This insecurity can be the result of a lack of training and a lack of leadership abilities and

gifts. Some of the church leaders in Ihechiowa, according to Diogu are always suspecting others around them, including their church members. One of such from Evangel Church will never accept any form of cooked food because he said that he is afraid of being poisoned, since he is not an indigene of Ihechiowa (*Oral Interview*). This shows that some of the church leaders have poor training, and that cause them to feel insecure when they come to pastor some places. To this, the church should have the goal to train authentic Church leaders who are capable of leading in such a way so that healthy cultures where people are treated with dignity and respect can develop and be maintained. McClung stresses the importance of offering education in leadership through seminars, educational programs and supervision, especially where the church place young, visionary people in leadership positions. This would be a means of providing support for leaders, resulting in higher self-esteem or confidence, and reducing insecurity (4).

ii. Lack of Mentorship for Church Leaders

Some of the church leaders in Ihechiowa find it hard to be under mentors, to be mentees. DePree emphasizes the importance of a mentoring relationship for one's development as a leader, and this is also applicable to church leaders (57). Joseph said that some of the church leaders in Ihechiowa do not have time to listen to advices from senior colleagues in the ministry. They see themselves as being able of taking care of whatsoever that comes their way (*Oral Interview*). He is convinced that a developing leader should have one or two mentors, and, later, become a mentor for someone else. Mentoring should include, on the one hand, learning from someone else's experience, and, on the other hand, provide a platform for accountability to another more senior person. Some of the church leaders in Ihechiowa do not have mentors who look after their ministerial growth and possibly calls them to order when they derails.

iii. Absence of Accountability

Absence of accountability among church leaders in Ihechiowa breeds abuse of power among them. A lack of accountability of the church leadership among leaders in Ihechiowa to those above them in the structure, or within a board or committee (can) harms healthy working relationships and lead to abuse of power. Sometimes, because these church leaders are not supervised, they find it easy to abuse their power. Uzodinma said that he had even told his church superintendent to look for a way to check the performances of pastors in their churches, but the process is still being delayed and as a result, there is high level of nuisance among their church leaders (*Oral Interview*). Kessler confirms that, because

human beings receive their authority from God, it is impossible to have authority without accountability for the use of this God-given authority. This includes accountability to other persons as well as to a board or similar head. McClung considers church leadership accountability to be the key to preventing the abuse of power in church leadership (4). Accountability is an integral aspect of ethical Christian leadership; Stahlke and Laughlin claim that accountability leads to affirmation for delivering the expected results. At the same time, accountability includes addressing and removing destructive and dysfunctional behaviour, which exposes or removes the abuser (4329).

iv. Poor Communication between Church leaders and Members

It was noticed by the researcher that communication is a major issue resulting to church leaders abusing their power in Ihechiowa. Decisions affecting members were made by church leadership without discussing the issues with them; people in the church felt their concerns were not heard; there was talking behind each others' backs. Some of the stories reveal that finances were mentioned as issues. Evidently finances do play an important role in abuse of power, but, as the stories reveal, finances are closely interwoven with other aspects of leadership, and are underlying motivations to justify the leader's actions. As one church leader stated, conflicts result because some members of the church "believe everything must be done perfectly, in their eyes, or not at all, while others feel that it is better to do something, rather than nothing. In these situations, the person/s that raised the most funding toward the project under discussion used that as leverage to get their way" (Njoku, *Oral Interview*).

v. Hypocritical Lifestyle

One of the reasons some Christian leaders abuse their power in Ihechiowa today, according to a respondent, is because of their ambition, or deluded desire, to compete with others who appear to be successful and such look for ways to achieve that. He said that some these leaders seem to come be in those positions without totally experiencing a deep relationship with God and do not allow the Holy Spirit to transform their lives for the better (Uchenna Okore, *Oral Interview*). He rehearsed that the Bible says that whatever we do, we should do it heartily (Col. 3:23) and our focus should be on pleasing the Lord, not receiving the accolades of what the world views as success. This type of hypocritical life which has not being totally yielded to God has caused some Christian leaders in some of these churches in Ihechiowa to desire things that do not really worth it in the ministry.

This brings a challenge in line with the assertion of Hagher in 2.9 where a Christian leader is seen as one that "...seeks to find God's will." This means that a hypocritical Christian leader seeks not God's will but his own selfish will. Thus, those Christian leaders who believe they have to become the best they can become so focused on attaining success in the world's eyes that they make decisions by looking for loopholes or shortcuts to quick numerical and statistical achievements and violate ethical Christian practices and proper protocol. Then, "when they have reached the pinnacle of their idea of success, they feel spiritually invincible and let their guard down, and that is when and where moral failure often takes root" as affirmed by Gaines (n.pg).

vi. Pressure

It has been observed that the Christian leadership demands a lot and every Christian leader is expected by the people to meet up with these demands. It ranges from helping others, evangelism, visitations, preaching, conducting indoor and outdoor church services to taking care of one's family and many others. Akuma pointed that the Christian leader has the duty of giving private and personal advice, looking after the people committed to his care, relieving people of their fears, et cetera (8). Omeukwu said that most times, their pastor makes mistakes as a result of the pressure the deacons and elders of the church mount on him; he is always made to go against his will, to their own holiness (*Oral Interview*). As a result of the demands of Christian leadership, some Christian leaders in Ihechiowa find themselves under situations that make them have unpleasant behaviours that make them abuse their power.

vii. Indiscipline

Indiscipline has to do with lacking discipline (the state of adherence to rules and conducts and having self-control). Indiscipline affects the life of a Christian leader so deeply that people would hardly see him as a role model or accept his teachings. This is true as Ekem said that some Church leaders in the Ihechiowa are yet to discipline themselves totally and to take control of their behaviours and emotions. Some of the church leaders quarrel with their church members, even from the pulpit, some speak ill of their members in public, some have being caught in shameful immoral acts that should not be mentioned around a minister of God (*Oral Interview*). Okereke added that lack of discipline among these leaders will render them to be one person to the some people and another to others another. It leads to inconsistency to their leadership (*Oral Interview*). Two respondents from two different churches lamented about the way their church leaders pick offense at every slightest provocation and

will even get ready to fight. One said that their church leader will always remind them of his anointing to curse and bless. Sometimes, he threatens to sue them to court. All these attitudes portrays indiscipline on the part of the church leader (Uchenna and Joseph, *Oral Interviews*).

viii. Greed

This is the excessive or reprehensive desire to acquire wealth; it is sometimes called covetousness in the scriptures (Brand 688). Some Christian leaders in Ihechiowa use their position to acquire wealth. They have allowed themselves to be controlled by the spirit of greed and dominancy, thereby placing money first before every other thing. They are ready to enrich themselves through every means. To them anything can go as long as money is concerned. Omeukwu lamented over this and told a story of one of such leader with such motive who dupes members of his church and runs after wealth, travelling nearly every week for one business or the other without minding the spiritual growth of his members. Much complaints spread around and the members started going to other churches. Consequently, in order to recover his members, he sought for power from a native doctor but later got exposed” (*Oral Interview*).

ix. Egotism

Okore said that “Egotism has also become rampant among Christian leaders in Ihechiowahave forgotten that God always opposes pride in any form (*Oral Interview*). An important question every Christian leader should ask is, “to whom are people drawn as the church ministry grows - me, a particular ministry or the Master (Christ)?” What Christian leaders need for progress is humility and holiness. When a Christian leader thinks he can do everything he will soon discover that he cannot do much. When a leader is selfish, he will be arrogant and he will always want to have his way in everything therefore he may not progress in his leadership journey. When a Christian leader thinks about the good of himself only, there is the possibility that he will not consider the situation of his members. This also implies that the leader becomes inconsiderate to issues regarding his members(Nnukwu, *Oral Interview*).

x. Cultural Misunderstandings

The wrong interpretation given to the cultures of the people of Ihechiowa by some of the Christian leaders has landed them into abuse of power, especially church leaders that are not indigenes of Ihechiowa. Some of these church leaders do not find it important to learn and listen to the reasons for

unfamiliar behaviour seen among the people. Benjamin said that some Christian leaders in Ihechiowa do not try to understand before being judgmental (*Oral Interview*). For instance, the marriage tradition of Ihechiowa people, whereby a married woman does not engage into any form of sexual act with another man, else the ancestors (Ndi Ichie) will take the life of the husband if she did not confess and sacrifice made early enough. Some of the Christian leaders have started preaching against this tradition to their members. They see it to be a terrible tradition. However, there may be a belief behind this practice, but these Christian leaders will not care to first get to know about it. When these church leaders begin to attack certain cultures of the people, it begins to breed misunderstanding between the church leader and the people. By this, the church leader starts to use his power to undermine the place of the people he has come to minister to.

xi. Lack of Experience

According to Uche, some of the church leaders in Ihechiowa fall into the error of abuse of power because they lack experience in church leadership. Some of these leaders are not teachable and will never want to take instructions from others. In some cases, when they are posted to a new church, they will not bend down to learn about the people and their ways of living (*Oral Interview*). Experience helps to shape the way a church leader handles issues, especially in a new environment. Not just their personal experiences, but also the one of others who had been there before them. The experience one gathers through life becomes a credit to him/her at most points in his/her life; it is also applicable to a church leader. Some of the church leaders in Ihechiowa failed in the area of use of their power because of lack of experience.

xii. Lack of Spiritual Maturity

Some of the church leaders in Ihechiowa abuse power in their respective churches because they are not spiritually grounded and stable. Some of them find it hard study the word of God which they are meant to teach the people of God. Some of them fail spiritually because of their prayerlessness. Okali said that one of their ministers do not come for Bible study but used that period to watch football match inside (*Oral Interview*). Prayer is one of the weapons a church leader can use to defeat the enemy. Therefore, a prayerless church leader apart from being spiritually powerless is also easily manipulated because the devil will manipulate him to rebel against the will of God. A prayerless church leader is prone to series of devilish manipulation. The first thing the devil does is to weaken a person's prayer life so that he can begin to afflict him. Today, it is sad to notice some church leaders' attitude toward prayer. They want

to have long sermon with short prayer; building project, soul winning with no prayer at all. Amah added that some of the church leaders in Ihechiowa hardly pray; some even fight against the prayer group so seriously that they would want no prayer group to exist in the church (like in their church) and this has led them to severe dangers in their church administration(*Oral Interview*).

4.4 Effects of Abuse of Power among Christian Leaders in Ihechiowa

Abuse of power has effects both on the church and the power of the gospel and on the abusive Christian leader himself.

4.4.1 On the Church

Goldingay has described Christian leaders as shepherds, having Christ as their Chief shepherd (345). As shepherds, Christian leaders in the Church must demonstrate professionalism and proper use of power so that church members can look up to them in trust and confidence, just as sheep look to a human shepherd for care, provision, protection, and guidance. But some insensitive and unprofessional church leaders in the church in Ihechiowa betray their people's trust and the essence of congregational ministry. Church members may find that some deeply personal issue they have shared with the minister becomes public knowledge as the theme of a sermon. Such public betrayal shakes people's confidence in their leaders in the church, and means that members will not share their struggles and hurts with them. Instead, they struggle on alone, and are at risk of being attracted to false shepherds.

Christian leaders in Ihechiowa with a distorted understanding of church leadership can also lead their flock into gross biblical and theological error. People may come to see prosperity, miracles and materialism as the essence of Christian spirituality. One of the respondents confirmed that in their church youths do not come for revival programs except if the preacher who was invited is a prosperity and miracle preacher (Uchenna Okore, *Oral Interview*). In a society, where the influence of African traditional religion is still pervasive, it is all too easy for people to substitute cult for conduct, and think that religious rituals and sacrifices guarantee salvation or impress God and earn his favour. Such error leads people to cloak dishonesty with noisy Christianity without spiritual productivity. This means that many people only come to church so that they will not be looked at as bad people but in the real sense, they are perpetrating evil in the society secretly.

Njoku lamenting on the effects of the abuse of power in the Church in Ihechiowa said that the outcomes are far-reaching. First of all, the victim can suffer a range of emotions that reflect the spiritual and emotional struggle: anger, sadness, lack of motivation, feelings of incompetency, withdrawal, resentment, devastation, depression, pain, feeling offended and excluded, and other ill emotions. She gave an illustration of a woman in their church that stopped coming to Church for the period of three years because the church leader sent to their church one Sunday embarrassed her by telling her to take her seat to sit beside the offering box while the sermon was going on because the church leader said that she was making noise (*Oral Interview*). However, the other members of the church may or may not recognize that the abuse is taking place. Some may be supportive, they may not get involved because of fear of abuse or of exposing another Christian's abusive behaviour and the consequences he/she may have to bear. Some may even tell the victim that the abusive behaviour is justifiable for the leader and the victim should submit to the leadership. One of the respondents said that some of the members of her Church nearly deceived her into believing that whatsoever the church leader says is to be done whether it is biblical or not, they claimed that the church leader will always have new revelations from God from time to time; however they never knew that the church leader was really making advances towards her and her daughter (Ugochukwu, *Oral interview*).

Emeka said that it is disheartening to observe that a number of these so-called church leaders in Ihechiowa seem to be in the ministry not because they were really called to the ministry but because they want to escape joblessness (*Oral interview*). This means that when the ministry is approached from a socio-economic perspective without significant emphasis on the biblical roots, ethical misconduct becomes obvious and such will include abuse of power. According to Diogu Albert, abuse of power among some church leaders in the some of the Churches in Ihechiowa has manifested itself in different ways. He affirmed thus, "We have heard reports from churches about the indiscreetful characters in the dealings of some church leaders of their Churches with their church members and funds; hardly any year passes without a bad report given in respect to abuse of power. In addition, the focus is always on moral failure such as church leaders using their power to commit sexual immorality, financial impropriety and unhealthy church relationship. However, we tend to forget equally debilitating behaviours such as anger, bitterness, envy, conspiracies, and ungodly competitions" (*Oral Interview*).

Still on the church, the gospel of Christ is hampered as a result of the abusive nature of the church leader. The gospel of Jesus Christ and his kingdom has inherent transforming power. It is expected that Christian leaders will lead their followers to transform society by their speech and lifestyle. The leader's failure in this regard greatly hampers the effective spread of the gospel. And the result will be that this corruption which is rampant in Nigerian society will spread to the church as a virus. Je'adayibe asserts that "when the church refuses to expose evil or keeps mute in the face of corruption, it has become corrupt itself" (442). This abuse of power by the church leader will weaken the prophetic voice of the church and it becomes hard for the church to be the conscience of society, because the power of the gospel has been made ineffectual in Ihechiowa community.

The effect of abuse of power among Christian leaders in Ihechiowa according a respondent has muddied the face of Christianity in Ihechiowa and detracted from the expected positive effects of Christian testimony and the gospel in the eyes of the bewildered watching public. The respondent also noted that the gospel has become anthropocentric rather than Christocentric and as a result, society sinks deeper into corruption and decay and, even worse, many souls are being lost (Joseph, *Oral Interview*). In addition, there is the certain loss of God's blessing and the potential loss of one's God-given family in Ihechiowa. These are the harsh realities of the cost of sin. Sin extracts a tremendous toll. A few moments of physical pleasure may produce a lifetime debt of shame and heartbreak. The cost is too great, the resulting pain not worth it.

4.4.2 On the Christian Leaders

Today some obvious negative consequences of abuse of power in Christian leadership in Ihechiowa are visible in the accusations leveled at those in clerical office and in the loss of integrity that has eroded respect for the Christian leaders in the eyes of some Christians and of the general the public. Sour and suspicious relationships, discord, and division among some Christian leaders also contribute to a decline in respect to their leadership.

When there is abuse of power among the church leaders, poor relationship emerges. Onyenachi, one of the respondents said that poor relationships was also responsible for the phenomenon of some church leaders refusing to work with their colleagues or enlist their co-operation and support (*Oral Interview*). Such church leaders do not respect, recognize, and appreciate the ministerial gifting and contributions of their colleagues.

A Christian leader who is not in close fellowship with God is vulnerable to temptations to indulge in sexual immorality or embezzlement of funds or other forms of or misconduct. When they succumb to these temptations, there is still further loss of respect for them and others. A respondent confirmed this by saying that one of the church leaders in their areas who was caught in adultery lost his respect in the community as many now make jest of his name, even inside the church while he is preaching (Okike, *Oral Interview*). To this, the leader losses his/her value. The Christian leadership should be a valuable vocation but whenever they lose the sight of rightful or moral living there is loss of value in the leadership.

The Christian leader also becomes ineffective for conversion of souls to God. Such a leader in the church will be suspected by others. The effect of abuse of power of a Christian leader on his family (in particular) is so much that some members of the family who may not have given their lives to Christ will bother not to do so because such scandal of a Christian leader if exposed will give them very bad impression that if Christianity is like that of his/hers, then it would be better for them to remain in the world. This will go a long way to discredit the leader in the church and the numerical strength of the church will be greatly affected and the world may begin to rate itself above the church.

Sometimes, the church members would begin to doubt the authenticity of the calling of the Church leader. They will become reluctant to follow his ideologies by restraining their support and financial involvement. Not just will the church have this problem of trust on their church leader but the church itself will be wrongly represented in the wilder society and the Church leader will be seen as a “joker” (an unserious person).

4.5 Lessons for Christian Leaders in Ihechiowa from Samuel’s Use of Power in 1 Samuel 12:1-5

Attention has been given to the practice of proper use of power as evident in the life and ministry of Samuel. His uprightness as par the material and monetary gifts he received as well as how he treated people was notable. The integrity Samuel built was neither automatic nor accidental. He worked it out. The question now is that how can the church leaders in Ihechiowa exercise their power in their respective churches without abusing it like Samuel.

i. Honesty and Diligence

Church leaders in Ihechiowa need live life of consistent honesty in words and action. They should be diligent so as to be able to resist moral failures. As church leader, they must be open to the workings of God in one and desire the will of God worked in and through their lives and application of classical Christian discipline in order to achieve the ministry that is built on integrity. Samuel was a man of truthfulness and diligence. He was true to his leadership duties and diligence in leading the people of God. And such helped him to be free of all abuses in office. Truly, as a man of like nature, Samuel would have been tempted many times (being a man of like passion) to do those things he asked them to testify against him for. Rather than allowing his desires to drive him, he learns to subdue the evil desires that arise from him. Today, there are specific cautions church leaders in Ihechiowa must take if they must avoid abuse of power. These are briefly discussed below:

ii. Nurturing One's Relationship with God

Church leaders in Ihechiowa should nurture their daily relationship with God. Daily relationship with God is an antidote for integrity crisis and a help to maintain ministerial integrity. Samuel must have maintained intimacy with Yahweh, the God of Israel. He was born of prayer and nurtured through prayer (1 Samuel 1:21-28, 2:1-10) and he gave his time to personal communion with God. This is evident in his constant intercession for Saul. As Yakubu puts it "his failure to intercede for the people would amount to sin" (Yakubu 21). That was where he received power to overcome all the leadership vulnerabilities. Contemporary church leaders in Ihechiowa must note that the only power source for a life of proper use of power is Jesus Christ. He must live in the church leader and direct his life. This means surrendering to His lordship. The church leader must withhold no area of his lives from His control. A daily personal communion with Jesus in the place of study and meditations over the world of God as well as prayers must be cultivated. It must be noted that it is in the presence of God that power for good church leadership is received.

iii. Life of Accountability

Just as Samuel submitted himself to the people of Israel to be testified for or against based on his leadership style, so church leaders in Ihechiowa should always be willing to submit themselves for accountability sake. They can even have accountability partners – these are senior colleagues or peers whom a church leader has submitted to and who can call him to order at any point he derails. This

relationship is very crucial for a church leader. As Pogwan puts it, it is a sign of dying as a church leader if one becomes unquestionable by anyone even when what he is doing is wrong (21). A church leader therefore must not get to the point of “always right”, a point at which he does things at will and in the way and time he desires to do them without anyone checking him.

iv. Trusting God for their Needs

Church leaders in Ihechiowa must as Samuel trust God for their needs. It is observed that some of the church leaders in Ihechiowa abuse their power as a result of them taking care of their needs by whatsoever means possible. God’s congregation is full of diverse people: the strong and the weak, the rich and the poor, there are the widows, the orphans, the jobless etc. God assigns the church leader to take care of all of them. However, the church leader is always in the temptation of using these people to satisfy his wants. He may want to feed on the fat, use the weak and enjoy the widows. It is advantageous to remember that God own the flock. His verdict is certain over shepherds (church leaders) who take advantage and so oppress the sheep.

v. Avoid Taking Advantage of God’s People

Church leaders in Ihechiowa, though may be faced with the temptation of this often but should avoid taking advantage of God’s people. Samuel in his leadership never did that. The prophecy of Ezekiel should not be the case of church leaders in Ihechiowa; wherein Ezekiel prophesied: “Son of man, prophesy against the shepherds of Israel, prophesy and say to them, 'Thus says the Lord God to the shepherds:’ Woe to the shepherds of Israel who feed themselves! Should not the shepherds feed the flocks? You eat the fat and clothe yourselves with the wool; you slaughter the fatlings, but you do not feed the flock. The weak you have not strengthened, nor have you healed those who were sick, nor bound up the broken, nor brought back what was driven away, nor sought what was lost; but with force and cruelty you have ruled them” (Ezekiel 34:2-4)

Truly, God uses the congregation and outsiders to meet the church leader’s needs in terms of gifts and donations. Samuel’s statement “*or from whose hand have I received any bribe with which to blind my eyes?*” connotes that he was probably offered such gift. Contemporary church leaders in Ihechiowa must therefore be wary of the kinds of gifts he takes. Odewole warns that questionable gifts offered as bribery to pervert justice must be rejected by the church leaders (56).

vi. Contentment in Ministry

Samuel was contented with what he had, so church leaders in Ihechiowa should take a stand against materialism but embrace contentment. The drive for material acquisition among the church leaders today is not news. This desire has eaten deep into the life and ministry of some church leaders today. There is the urge to make millions, travel abroad, get latest cars, build an ultra modern auditorium and personal house etc. The scriptural assertion is clear “for the love of money is a root of all kinds of evil, for which some have strayed from the faith in their greediness, and pierced themselves through with many sorrows” (1 Tim 6:10). The writer of Hebrews therefore warns “let your conduct be without covetousness; be content with such things as you have. For God Himself has said, "I will never leave you nor forsake you."(Heb 13:5). Samuel’s life was free of materialism, so he never abused his power as a leader of the people of God. In the same manner, contentment should then be the hallmark of the church leaders in Ihechiowa.

4.6 Other Strategies for Preventing Abuse of Power among Christian Leaders in Ihechiowa

Such strategies include the following:

i. Creation of Awareness on Power Abuse

Uche observed that most times, when there are signals of abuse of power in the church, none seems to see it until it starts to affect the members of the church. Not that they are not seeing it but they do not want to talk about it (*Oral Interview*). So, church leaders and members in these churches in Ihechiowa must become aware of the situations that are contributing to the abuse of power. This awareness must result in the acceptance that the abuse of power is a danger and a reality, even in the church, and must become a topic for discussion. It cannot be ignored. Nunez and Gonzalez explain the necessity for developing mechanics and models to expose, explain and deter abuse in Christian institutions (48). Okereke said that “When the church members pretend that nothing is happening it becomes hard for a preventive measure to be taken or solution sought for. It will further expose the victims to more danger, but when the awareness is created; a platform is set to address the abuse” (*Oral Interview*).

ii. Emphasis on the Scripture

Njasi said that the Word of God should be the compass for church leadership and church leaders in Ihechiowa should see and use it as such. For her, it is because the church leaders in Ihechiowa do not

take the Word of God serious that is why they abuse their power (*Oral Interview*). This means that the Authority of Scripture must be emphasized among Church Christian leaders in Ihechiowa to help them lead well. The dissenting cry of sola scriptura affirms the first biblical power base. Incidentally, this rallying cry was a reaction to leadership power abuse. For Protestantism, and especially for Evangelicals, the authority of scripture must remain the basis for Godly authority and spiritual power. This authoritative privilege is attributed to scripture, because it alone speaks truthfully about God, mankind, and creation.

iii. Embrace of Humility

According to John, Ihechiowa Church leaders should embrace humility in their service as stewards of Christ if the problem of abuse of power among them must be prevented (*Oral Interview*). The task of the leader, as an interpreter of God's word, is to expound the scriptures as clearly as possible, so they are understood and responded to accordingly. But the leader, and his or her audience, are on an equal footing before the scriptures, and must listen with open and expectant hearts, and with much prayer. Even though the leader has a privileged task of studying and interpreting God's word, he or she must never try to equate God's word with his or her own interpretation. As Pope Gregory iterated: "A leader is only a servant of God, above all else" (71). And this, the church leaders in Ihechiowa need to understand.

iv. Firm and Discretional Application of Discipline

Discipline is also necessary for every Christian leader in the church in Ihechiowa if the issue of abuse of power among some church Christian leaders must be prevented in Ihechiowa. The church, according to one of the respondents, should be firm and discretional in applying discipline to its church leaders in Ihechiowa. They are to be firm in the sense that such behaviours that portray abuse of power among the Church leaders should have retribution in order to correct the persons involved and to deter others from getting involved in such behaviours. In addition, the church should be discretional in the sense that any case involving matters of abuse of power should be handled on its own merit. Okali speaking on discipline said that those church leaders who in one way or the other are caught in either sexual immorality, misappropriation of church fund or others should be dealt with by the Church court or governing body, not minding the level of the person in the church. This will make church leaders in these churches to be serious with their work and lead them to be examples of discipline to their members (*Oral Interview*).

v. Reliance on the Holy Spirit

Okali also added that, the Holy Spirit is the greatest teacher and the church leaders in Ihechiowa need to rely on the help of the Holy spirit to be good leaders in the Church of God (*Oral Interview*). The Holy Spirit provides the other basis for Christian authority and power. Since, He originally inspired the writers of scripture; He also authenticates the authoritative ring of scripture, giving it life and power, so believe that, based on careful exegesis, we are realistically only presented with these two complementary bases. On the eve of His departure, Jesus pledged the Holy Spirit to His disciples, to help them in the task of world mission. “But you will receive power, when the Holy Spirit comes on you; you will be witnesses in Jerusalem, in all Judea and Samaria, and to the ends of the earth.” The Holy Spirit, then, is the true leader in the work of God’s mission on earth. He provides direction, the gifts-mix, and empowers the church to carry out this mission. How vital it is for the Holy Spirit to energize the leader in his or her role in the local church. But human power and scheming must yield completely, before the Spirit’s enabling power can be experienced in its fullness. Anyone who attempts to lead God’s people, without the aid of the Holy Spirit, is simply an abusive hireling.

vi. Proper Screening for Church Leaders’ Training

It was discovered by the researcher that each of these churches in Ihechiowa own pastoral or theological schools where their church leaders are trained for the ministerial work. Some of them earn certificate, diploma or degree at the end of their study. It is necessary that applicants for pastoral training into these schools owned by these churches be properly screened. This entails that not every kind of person should be admitted into the Church pastoral training schools. Any person that should be admitted must be first regenerated. In line with this, Uzodinma said that, ‘these Churches should be more careful in the selection of its students for pastoral training because the life of a church leader must be without blemish. So, the lives of aspirants should be evaluated right from the congregation level before being allowed to be enrolled for pastoral training’ (*Oral Interview*). There is the necessity of this because if a Christian leader while being a student in the school imbibes good morals, it would be hard for the person to live life of dishonesty or compromise in the field. If this is done, the pastoral work will not be looked down on as a business any kind of person can get into for gain. It will bring more respect to church leadership training.

vii. Strong and Effective Counseling for Church Leaders in Ihechiowa

Counseling the church leaders in Ihechiowa from time to time through seminars, retreats or conferences by their respective churches will go a long way to help listen to them and proffer solutions to problems in their marital lives and homes. Emeka trying to highlight the need for counseling here cited the case of a church leader from Divine Foundation Church who died as a result of drunkenness. To this, he said that that church leader might have being saved from the death that came his way if he had a counselor to speak to him. Under this, he emphasized more on organizing marriage seminars for the church leaders in Ihechiowa, as they are always cases of adultery recorded against them in their respective Churches (*Oral Interview*). Seminars on the way to handle church funds will also be beneficial to them.

viii. Theological Understanding of the Biblical Standards for Church Leadership

Diogu pointed that Church leaders in churches in Ihechiowa need to gain and regain the biblical standard for the Christian leadership. He emphasized that four major texts address God's qualifications for service: Acts 20:28-35; 1 Tim. 3:1-7; Titus 1:5-9; and 1 Pet. 5:1-4; all are needed for this knowledge. It is essential that church leaders adopt the biblical model as opposed to the secular model for church leadership(*Oral Interview*). Church leaders in Ihechiowa need to repent of the sin of failure to follow the biblical pattern of a shepherd-leader and church leader-teacher, and then determine deep within with fervent conviction and courage never again to deviate from the divine pattern(Joseph, *Oral Interview*). This will mean taking very seriously the charge to be a "one woman kind of man" and to be one "who manages his own household well," and to be one who has "a good testimony among those who are outside" the church (1 Tim. 3:1-7). It will mean pursuing diligently God's call to holiness and purity (1 Pet. 1:15-16). When the church leaders in Ihechiowa understand what the Bible really says about their kind of leadership, they would not live double-faced lives.

ix. Strategic Supervision of Ministers by the Church Governing Bodies

Amah said that Church leaders working in Ihechiowa need to be strategically supervised by their Church governing bodies. Church leaders are not to be left unsupervised. As they are accountable to the church governing bodies, concerning the congregations they are in charge of, more interest should be given to the supervision of their works. This will help to prevent church leaders from ill behavior (*Oral Interview*). Orie also added that the members of the committee who are to be watchdogs are not to be

sentimental in the information they provide to the church on characters of the church leaders (*Oral Interview*).

x. Strict Observance of Established of Ethical Code of Conduct for Church Leaders

It was noticed by the researcher that all the churches in Ihechiowa have code of conduct for its church leaders. But it seems that strict observance is not given to these rules and regulations. These churches should encourage their church leaders to maintain the code of conduct. A code of ministerial ethics will help provide a clear and written standard of performance that congregations with similar beliefs can adopt. The Code of Ethics for Church Leaders directly addresses many of the contemporary scandals and issues associated with churches, such as sexual improprieties and the mishandling of funds. From this, it is clear to note that ethical code of conduct for church leaders will help to guide their behaviour towards achieving success in their leadership in the church and the church as a body would not be a laughing stock to the unbelievers.

CHAPTER FIVE

SUMMARY AND CONCLUSION

The chapter begins with a summary of the findings made generally by the study, followed by recommendations to the church, the church leaders and the victims of abuse of power. The contribution of this research to knowledge is also reflected. The chapter also gave suggestions for further research as part of the purposes stated in 1.5 (number 7 of the purpose of the study) and the conclusion ends the chapter.

5.1 Summary

At the end of the research, the following findings were made:

1. There is abuse of power among church leaders in Ihechiowa and that manifests in several ways such as, playing God, wrong use of authority through coercion, suppressions, spiritual pride, financial misappropriation, manifestation of other unethical behaviours, etc.
2. The causes of abuse of power among church leaders in Ihechiowa can be traceable to insecurity, lack of mentorship for church leaders, absence of accountability, poor communication between church leaders and members, indiscipline, lack of experience, lack of spiritual maturity, and others.
3. The effects of abuse on the church were that the members' confidence will be betrayed, gross biblical error, spiritual and emotional struggle, the power of the gospel will be diminished and the church becomes a laughing stock to unbelievers.
4. The effects of the abuse on the church leader himself were poor relationships, vulnerability to temptations, suspicion and doubt concerning his/her leadership.
5. The acceptable behavior expected of church leaders in Ihechiowa are those as reflected in Samuel's lifestyle of accountability, honesty, contentment, etc.
6. There are other strategies which can help Christian leaders in Ihechiowa to prevent power abuse.

5.2 Recommendations

In this research, it is therefore recommended that:

1. Church leaders in Ihechiowa should embrace humility and rely totally on the Holy Spirit for success in their leadership.

2. The scripture should be the only guide to the church leaders in Ihechiowa for their practice of leadership.
3. Church members of the churches in Ihechiowa should speak out when they notice any abuse of power by their church leaders.
4. Church leaders in Ihechiowa need to constantly submit themselves for appraisal for accountability by the church, which should be done either privately or through random sampling of their members' perceptions of them.
5. Men and women who aspire to be leaders in the church should be properly scrutinized before they are given such responsibilities by the church.
6. Churches in Ihechiowa should be discreet in their application of discipline for the church leaders who abuse their power in different areas of their leadership in the church.
7. The churches in Ihechiowa should always organize counseling for the church leaders who are facing different challenges in their churches. This will help to avoid them using their power wrongly while trying to handle such situations.
8. Strategic supervision should be employed by church boards to enable check the ministry of the church leaders; this will enhance accountability among church leaders in Ihechiowa.
9. Church leaders in Ihechiowa should observe the ethical code of conduct governing their ministerial life as church leaders.
10. Members of the churches in Ihechiowa should see the need to take good care of their church leaders as this will help them to overcome certain temptations concerning money and it will help the church. The remuneration of church leaders should be improved and adequate welfare packages should be put in place for their families.
11. Church leaders in Ihechiowa should maintain good Christian life worthy of a Christian leader by shunning hypocritical lifestyle, greed and pride and other forms of indiscipline.

5.3 Contributions to Knowledge

The research will contribute to knowledge by creating the awareness that there is the reality of abuse of power in church Christian leadership in Ihechiowa. It exposed abuse of power, not just in any other Christian institution or organization but in the church; so, it will be a relevant material for researchers who will have interest in this area. It will benefit Christian leaders in and outside Ihechiowa by alerting them of abuse of power and its dangers and ways of handling it. It also showed how the life and

ministry of Samuel in 1 Samuel 12:1-5 can be an example for church leaders in using their power properly in the church.

5.4 Suggestion for Further Studies

As a result of the delimitation of the research, some areas concerning the church leaders and their leadership in Ihechiowa were not covered in this research and some other areas were not treated in full, thus the researcher sincerely suggests the following for further studies as it would elucidate more on the work:

1. Role of Church Authority in Curbing Sexual Abuse among Christian Leaders in Ihechiowa.
2. Financial Misappropriation among Christian Leaders in Ihechiowa: The Way forward.
3. The Need for Accountability and Stewardship among Ihechiowa Christian Leaders.
4. The Effects of Counseling in Christian Leadership in Ihechiowa.

5.5 Conclusion

This research has explored the issue of abuse of power Christian leadership in Ihechiowa, especially in the church. This abuse is a traumatic process of unethical manipulation and domination, intentionally inflicted by some church leaders upon their members in Ihechiowa. This control is achieved through various manipulative forms of actual mind control. Leadership power abuse in the churches may not be reported, but the researcher believes that it is more pervasive than assumed. Perhaps this problem is contributing significantly to the ineffectiveness of some of the churches in Ihechiowa. Some pastors give in to egoistic thinking and develop wounding habits. This is contrary to the concept of liberating power that is taught in the Scripture and seen in the leadership lifestyle of Samuel in 1 Samuel 12:1-5. Abuse of power turns the church from a sanctuary into a prison; the faith which should lead to ultimate freedom becomes an ultimate trap in Ihechiowa. It is vital, therefore, for churches in Ihechiowa to be aware of the problem, and to deal with it accordingly. However, this conclusion does not negate the fact that God has given power to the church leader and that the Bible demands that members submit to God-called Christian leaders in the church who are leading according to God's word. And that some church leaders abuse their power is not a license for church members to become rebellious toward genuine God-given leadership. The research submits that if these recommendations given in this research are followed effectively, then abuse of power will be curbed in Christian leadership in Ihechiowa.

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APPENDIX

LIST OF PEOPLE INTERVIEWED FROM SIX CHURCHES IN IHECHIOWA

NAME	GENDER	AGE	OCCUPATION	CHURCH	DATE INTERVIEWED
Amah, Kalu	M	53	Civil Servant	T.A.C	29/09/2022
Charles, Rev. Njoku	M	42	Clergy	E.C	15/10/2022
Diogu, Rev. Albert	M	50	Clergy	P.C.N	13/09/2022
Ekem, Kalu	M	62	Businessman	A.G.C	17/09/2022
Imo, Beatrice	F	50	Businesswoman	D.F.C	10/09/2022
John, Janet	F	44	Businesswoman	A.G.C	17/09/2022
Joseph, Emeka	M	48	Civil Servant	D.F.C	10/09/2022
Joseph, Orié	M	78	Engineer	P.C.N	13/09/2022
Kalu, Sunday	M	41	Mercenary	D.F.C	10/09/2022
Njasi, Martina	F	47	Trader	P.C.N	14/09/2022
Njoku, Florence	F	33	Businesswoman	T.A.C	29/09/2022
Nnennaya Orié	F	48	Farmer	P.C.N	14/09/2022
Nnukwu, Amah	M	45	Businessman	T.A.C	29/09/2022
Okali, Comfort	F	42	Civil Servant	P.C.N	19/09/2022
Okereke, Margaret	F	67	Farmer	A.G.C	17/09/2022
Okike, Mgbechi	F	38	Farmer	C.A.C	17/10/2022
Okore, Uchenna	M	43	Civil Servant	E.C	17/10/2022
Okwuagwu, Okey	M	52	Businessman	E.C	17/10/2022
Omeukwu, Janet	F	43	Farmer	T.A.C	29/09/2022
Oti, Nneoke	F	79	Farmer	E.C	15/10/2022
Pst. Onyenachi David	M	38	Clergy	C.A.C.	17/10/2022
Uche, Benjamin	M	51	Tailor	P.C.N	21/09/2022
Uchenna, Emmanuel	M	42	Doctor	A.G.C	17/09/2022
Ugochukwu, Amarachi	F	25	Businesswoman	P.C.N	21/09/2022
Uzodinma, Rev. Francis	M	51	Clergy	A.G.C	17/09/2022

Abbreviation Meanings:

P.C.N—The Presbyterian Church of Nigeria
 A.G.C—Assemblies of God Church
 E.C—Evangel Church

D.F.C—Divine Foundation Church
 T.A.C—The Apostolic Church
 C.A.C—Christ Ascension Church